

Protocol for a Systematic Literature Review on the Evaluation of Code Recommender Systems

Institute for Complex Networks
Vienna University of Economics and Business (WU Vienna)

Authors

Daniel Borst daniel.borst@wu.ac.at
Stefan Sobernig stefan.sobernig@wu.ac.at

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Credits Authorship Contribution Statement

Contributor Name	Affiliation	Contributions
Daniel Borst	Vienna University of Economics and Business	Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal Analysis, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualization, Project Administration
Stefan Sobernig	Vienna University of Economics and Business	Validation, Data Curation, Writing – Review and Editing, Supervision, Project Administration
Kevin Innerebner	Graz University of Technology	Data Curation
Florian Poreba	Vienna University of Economics and Business	Data Curation
Leonie Greber	Vienna University of Economics and Business	Data Curation
Mark Strembeck	Vienna University of Economics and Business	Validation

Document History

Version 1	Initial document, top-level structure adapted from Kitchenham et al., Zhang et al., and Wohlin et al..	Daniel Borst, Apr. 2024
Version 2	Initial data extraction and selection criteria scheme; Development of research questions based on PICOC model as proposed by Petticrew and Roberts; Adding background section on prior research stages leading to this SLR.	Daniel Borst, May 2024
Version 3	Description of pilot literature search; Results from pilot study including tabulars and figures; Development of search string; Adding results from engine capabilities assessment.	Daniel Borst, Jun. 2024
Version 4	Revision of "Selection Criteria" and "Data Extraction" section; Adding research questions four.	Daniel Borst, Jun. 2024
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Version 8	Adding "Performing Engine Searches" section; Including statistical analysis for "Post-processing Result Sets" section; Adapting the selection criteria process.	Daniel Borst, Nov. 2024
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Version 10	Including statistical analysis for "Selection Criteria" and "Quality Assessment" section; Refinement of "Reliability" section for data extraction; Adding further separation of metrics' measurement objectives into sub-characteristics.	Daniel Borst, Sep. 2025
Version 11	Including statistical analysis for "Data Extraction" section; Insights and adaption to the data extraction process from the discussion round; Refinements to the data analysis.	Daniel Borst, Oct. 2025

On this Document

This document outlines the protocol for conducting a systematic literature review (SLR) aimed at analyzing evaluation methods used to assess the impact of code recommender systems. Serving as supplemental material to a manuscript submitted for publication, this protocol should be read alongside the manuscript to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the SLR's execution and to facilitate potential replication. It is important to note that, without the contextual background provided by the manuscript, the protocol may be difficult to interpret on its own. A publicly available replication package, including all data, scripts, and materials used in this SLR, is provided to ensure full transparency and reproducibility.

Format and Notation.

This protocol employs a dual-layered approach to document its contents. Primarily, it outlines the SLR process within the main body of text, where all planned procedural steps are systematically presented across various sections and paragraphs. Additionally, any deviations from these initial plans observed during the SLR execution, alongside intermediate outcomes such as selection rationales and data handling procedures, are captured in distinct text blocks shaded in grey. These include supplementary materials like data tables and illustrative figures, positioned immediately after the relevant sections of the main text for coherence.

Furthermore, within Sections 2 and 4, specific word groups are visually modified (e.g., underlined, struck through) to indicate their inclusion or exclusion in the development of the search string for the SLR's automated database search. It's important to note that these stylistic modifications are not indicators of textual revisions or updates but are instead employed to enhance the reader's understanding of the search strategy formulation process.

0.1 Background: Early, Preparatory Research Stages

Drafting the Review Protocol and Pilot.

In our pursuit to systematically analyze evaluation methods for assessing the impact of code recommender systems, we initially aimed to identify existing secondary studies such as literature surveys or systematic reviews that could inform or partially contribute to our research design. Our search revealed several secondary studies on code recommender systems, primarily focusing on the classification of these systems, their functionalities, limitations, underlying design and architecture, and applications.

Despite the presence of six related secondary studies (see Table 1), we found that none specifically concentrated on the evaluation of code recommender systems as their primary focus. The studies did touch upon evaluation methods, but these discussions were brief and not the central theme of the reviews. Moreover, these studies were limited to specific software engineering domains, such as modeling-driven engineering [1], which did not fully align with our need for an examination of the whole field of code recommender system evaluation. Additionally, another study dealing with the evaluation of general recommender systems [2] lacked the necessary context within software engineering.

Given the lack of directly applicable precedents, we decided to establish a new SLR protocol tailored specifically to our research questions. Our approach to developing this SLR protocol was guided by the review procedures and guidelines proposed by Kitchenham et al. [3], Wohlin et al. [4], and Zhang et al. [5]. To validate and refine the protocol, we applied parts of it in a pilot study aimed at identifying seed papers for the quasi-gold standard corpus. This pilot study also provided valuable insights that led to revisions of the review protocol.

1 Motivation

A substantial body of literature has extensively explored various facets of code recommender systems, including their application, design, classification, and the underlying technologies that drive their functionality (see, e.g., [6]–[9]). Code recommender systems are defined as systems that provide a developer with automated suggestions in the context of language services, encompassing both syntactic aspects like static program analysis and semantic aspects such as automated code generation, aimed at enhancing work practices and outcomes. These systems, which range from simple algorithms to advanced models, have become increasingly popular in the software engineering industry [10], [11]. Technological improvements, such as the integration of advanced computational techniques in tools like GitHub Copilot have expanded the capabilities of these systems, enabling more complex operations such as generating code from natural language descriptions, automating programming tasks, and fixing buggy code snippets [12], [13].

In this paper, our focus is on evaluating code recommender systems. We define evaluation as a systematic determination of an artifact’s quality typically involving an additional data source such as human participants. It often includes validation to ensure the artifact functions correctly before assessing its impact in context. Validating means determining an artifact’s quality via direct observation and measurement, independent of external input. According to Zangerle and Bauer [14], evaluation methods for recommender systems can be categorized into offline evaluations, online evaluations, and user studies. Offline evaluations involve simulating user behavior based on past interactions, allowing researchers to evaluate the system without involving human subjects, using only simulated tasks. In contrast, online evaluations use field experiments where users carry out their self-selected tasks in a real-world setting. Finally, user studies are conducted with human participants, either in live or controlled laboratory settings, where individuals perform tasks designed by the researcher. Each of these methods provides unique insights.

Evaluating code recommender systems is crucial for providing empirical evidence of their impact on developers’ productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, and satisfaction. Such evaluations are essential for guiding the design of more effective code recommender systems tailored to developers’ needs and experiences [15], [16]. Typically, these evaluations are conducted through offline experiments, online experiments, and user studies. Each evaluation method offers unique insights but also presents specific limitations. The selection of the right method for the appropriate technology and context is crucial, as inadequate or inappropriate evaluation methods can lead to misleading conclusions about the impacts of these systems [1], [2], [15].

Despite the importance of evaluation, there has been no SLR focusing primarily on the evaluation of code recommender systems. Existing reviews only address the evaluation aspect as a minor part of their overall scope (see e.g., [1], [12], [16]–[19]). Moreover, these reviews are limited to specific types of code recommender systems, such as those for model-driven engineering [1] or code recommender systems based on advanced computational techniques [16]–[18], and lack depth in their evaluation discussions.

Prior to this SLR analyzed literature reports that evaluations for code recommender systems mainly rely on offline studies [13], [16]. While these methods offer controlled environments, they often create a gap between the promised and actual results when applied in real-world scenarios. Offline evaluations typically fail to capture the dynamic, contextual nature of real-world development environments and do not involve human programmers, resulting in potentially unrealistic assessments [13], [16].

We propose a systematic review of scientific publications focusing on the evaluation of code recommender systems across various software languages (see Section 7.1). The aim of this review is to determine the prevalence of different evaluation methods used and to examine how these methods are employed to evaluate the impact of code recommender systems in software development. Additionally, this review will identify the quality attributes and corresponding metrics used in various evaluation methods. Metrics are understood as higher-level, somewhat subjective attributes often based on quantifiable, observable, and objective data [20]. By doing so, we aim to highlight areas where future research should be directed and provide an overview of existing methods to support the development of a framework for the evaluation of code recommender systems.

2 Research Questions

For defining our research questions, we followed the PICOC (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, Context) model as proposed by Petticrew and Roberts [21]. The PICOC model ensures a structured approach to formulating comprehensive and clear research questions. The components of the PICOC model in the context of our SLR are defined as follows:

- *Population*: Systems and operations that support software engineering activities specifically related to software language code.
- *Intervention*: The measurement of the impact of recommendation systems that support the creation or modification of software language code (code recommender systems).
- *Comparison*: The process of creating or modifying software language code without the support of recommendation systems.
- *Outcome*: Characterization of the quality attributes and evaluation methods used, their prevalence, and their effectiveness and efficiency in assessing the impact of code recommender systems.
- *Context*: Any context in which developers create or modify software language code.

Our motivation is to provide an overview of evaluation methods for code recommender systems to identify areas for future research and to build a foundation for developing a new framework that addresses the practical challenges of evaluating these systems in dynamic and diverse programming environments. Therefore, our research questions are:

- **RQ1** What is the prevalence of offline *studies^e*, online *studies^e*, and user *studies^e* as *evaluation^e* methods for *code recommender^{a,t}* systems?
- **RQ2** How are different *evaluation^e* methods used to *assess^e* the impact of *code recommender^{a,t}* systems in *software development^s*?
- **RQ3** What metrics are employed to *assess^e* the impact of *code recommender^{a,t}* systems?
- **RQ4** Which threats to validity and limitations are reported in studies evaluating code recommender systems?

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Research question 4 was added after the search string had already been defined, which is why it was not considered during the search string formulation. However, RQ4 focuses on reported threats to validity in the identified studies, an aspect that does not directly affect the search string definition. The search string was designed to identify studies evaluating code recommender systems, and the inclusion of RQ4 does not alter the scope or keywords required for that process.

V. 7

Based on the framework by Kitchenham and Brereton [22], the scope of this study was determined. The goal of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of how CRSs are evaluated. While aspects of CRS evaluation have been considered in prior SMS [1], SLRs [2], [12], [17], [19], and non-systematic reviews [16], [18], [23], this is typically done only as a minor or secondary focus. These studies are not from the CRS domain itself but from broader areas such as the evaluation of RSs in general [2], from more specialized domains like RSs in MDE [1], or from subsets of CRS such as code generation with LLMs [16] or AI-assisted programming tasks [23]. To address this gap, we adopt the design of a SLR, which enables us to capture, classify, and synthesize all relevant primary studies.

3 Overview

To address the research questions outlined above, we conduct a SLR containing the following steps:

1. *Preparation*: In preparation for our SLR, we strived to identify comparable secondary studies on the same or similar subjects. To ensure a comprehensive and unbiased collection of relevant papers, we utilized Google Scholar as our search engine. Search terms were derived from our research questions, incorporating synonyms to capture relevant terminology. The search terms used, along with the corresponding found secondary literature, are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of secondary literature identified via Google Scholar, including venues, publishers, scope (as indicated by the studies’ authors), and search terms.

Venue	Publisher	Publication	Scope (as indicated by authors)	Search Term
Softw. Syst. Model.	Springer	[1]	Mapping Review	Evaluation code recommender system
MedAI	IEEE	[16]	Review	Evaluation code generation system
IEEE Access	IEEE	[17]	Systematic Review	Evaluation code generation system
TEM	UIKTEN	[18]	Comparative Review	Evaluation code generation system
ArXiv	ArXiv	[12]	Survey	Evaluation code intelligence system
ICSESS	IEEE	[19]	Systematic Literature Review	Evaluation software assistants

Our search revealed literature that focuses on specific aspects of code recommender systems, such as design, architecture, functionalities, applications, or limitations. While some of these studies touch upon evaluation, they do so only briefly. Additionally, most studies focus on specific types of code recommender systems, such as those used in model-driven engineering [1], or AI-based code recommender systems [16]–[18]. The diversity of targeted systems is especially evident when comparing the supported tasks across publications (see Table 13). Consequently, these studies did not qualify as direct review designs for our SLR.

2. *Establishing a quasi-gold standard (QGS) corpus*: The initial step involves building a QGS corpus of reference publications as proposed by Zhang et al. [5]. The QGS serves as a benchmark for evaluating the quality of the automated search. By calculating the quasi-sensitivity, we can assess the performance of the automated search and iteratively refine the search string. To create the QGS corpus, we will slightly modify Zhang’s [5] proposed strategy. Instead of manually searching selected top publication venues in the field, we will employ a combination of an automated search using Google Scholar and backward snowballing from secondary literature to compile relevant publications. The detailed procedures for creating the QGS are outlined in Section 4 of this document.

3. *Performing the automated search:* For the automated search, we will start by following the established search strategy detailed in Section 4. We will define an initial set of search terms and continuously refine them to ensure they capture all relevant studies. These search terms will be translated into representations compatible with the specific syntax and requirements of each search engine. We will then execute individual search operations across various search engines and systematically collect the results in a format suitable for further processing and analysis. The automated search will be concluded once we reach the quasi-sensitivity threshold. Quasi-sensitivity is defined as the proportion of relevant papers (QGS papers) retrieved by an automated search relative to the size of the QGS corpus. According to the guidelines, a desired target quasi-sensitivity threshold is set between 70% and 80% [5].
4. *Performing the first literature review:* Our SLR involves filtering the search results based on predefined selection criteria, as outlined in Section 6. Subsequently, design-decision data will be extracted from the selected studies (see Section 7).
5. *Performing backward snowballing:* Alongside the automated search, we will manually review the bibliographies (i.e. reference sections) of the publications identified. This backward snowballing approach aims to broaden the scope of our SLR, ensuring we capture all relevant code recommender evaluation publications. This method helps mitigate the risk of missing significant studies [4]. Additional details on this process can be found in Section 5.
6. *Performing a second literature review:* In the final step, we will review the results obtained from the snowballing process. This involves applying the same selection criteria and extracting data according to our guidelines detailed in Section 7.

Throughout the review process, we will strictly adhere to established guidelines for the design, conduct, and reporting of SLRs, particularly those referenced in [3]–[5]. Additionally, we will apply recognized statistical methods for inter-rater reliability (IRR) analysis, such as the Cohen’s Weighted Kappa coefficient ($\hat{\kappa}_c$) [24], to accurately measure and report the levels of agreement and disagreement among the experts involved in the inclusion/exclusion of publications and the extraction of design decisions.

4 Search Strategy

4.1 Pilot Literature Search

To ensure the robustness of our protocol, we conducted a pilot literature search. This preliminary step helps identify and correct potential errors in data collection and processing. Additionally, it may reveal the necessity for methodological adjustments, such as refining data extraction procedures and synthesis techniques, to better address our research questions [3].

1. *Automated search:* We employed the PICOC method [21] to categorize our search terms. To maximize recall we focused only on population, intervention, and context, while trying to keep the terms as general as possible. From the intervention category, we included terminology related to evaluation processes (*evaluation^e*). For the context, we selected terminology associated with software engineering (*software engineering^s*). For the population, we created two sets of search terms: one for tools (*tool^t*) supporting developers and another for actions (*action^a*) provided by the tools. To further maximize recall, we used two distinct search strings: one incorporating the categories: evaluation, software engineering, and tools, and the other: evaluation, software engineering, and actions. The terms for the search strings were extracted from the following two sources:
 - (a) *Research questions:* Extract critical terms from the research questions. Selected terms are highlighted in Section 2.
 - (b) *Secondary studies:* Mine critical terms from the title, abstract, and keywords (if any) from the six secondary studies (see Section 3).

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The following candidate search terms were extracted from the titles, abstracts, and keywords of the secondary studies:

- [1] ~~Recommender~~, ~~evaluation methods~~, software *engineering*^s, *study*^e
- [16] *Code Generation*^a, *Evaluation*^e, computer *science*^s, software *engineering*^s, *studies*^e, *code completion*^a
- [17] *Code Generation*^a, *programming*^s, ~~Automatic software development~~, *evaluating*^e
- [18] ~~Automated Code Generation~~, *ACG*, *Software Development*^s, computer *science*^s, ~~evaluation metrics~~, ~~evaluation criteria~~
- [12] *Code Intelligence*^t, ~~source code generation~~, *Code Generation*^a, ~~Source code generation~~, ~~performance evaluation~~
- [19] ~~Assistant~~, Software *Engineering*^s, ~~assistants~~, developing *assistants*^t, *evaluation*^e, *recommendation*

After merging the search terms from the secondary studies with those from the research questions, data cleansing was carried out through the following steps:

- Removal of duplicates (strikethrough)
- Removal of redundant terms (strikethrough)
- Conversion of plural to singular forms
- Addition of alternative noun forms for gerunds
- Conversion of uppercase to lowercase writing

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Listing 1: First search string used for the initial automated search

("code generation" **OR** "code recommendation" **OR** "code completion") **AND** ("evaluation" **OR** "assessment" **OR** "study") **AND** ("software engineering" **OR** "software development" **OR** " computer science" **OR** "programming")

The first search string is constructed from three categories: action, evaluation, and software engineering. It contains 10 distinct search terms, leading to 36 unique search triples.

Listing 2: Second search string used for the initial automated search

("code recommender" **OR** "code intelligence" **OR** "developing assistant") **AND** ("evaluation" **OR** "assessment" **OR** "study") **AND** ("software engineering" **OR** "software development" **OR** " computer science" **OR** "programming")

The second search string is built from the categories tool, evaluation, and software engineering. It includes 10 different search terms, resulting in an additional 36 unique search triples.

To ensure a comprehensive and unbiased collection of relevant papers, we used Google Scholar to search with the two strings [4]. We applied a time filter to include papers published from 2017 to the present, in line with our inclusion/exclusion criteria. To limit the scope, we only considered results from the first 30 pages. Additionally, the first author analyzed the results from both search strings for relevance and made a preselection for further evaluation.

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The search, conducted on July 16, 2024, resulted in 20 studies for the first search string and 7 studies for the second.

2. *Backward snowballing*: Following the guidelines by Wohlin [4], the first step in this process is to generate a start set. To avoid bias towards any specific publisher, it is recommended to use a publisher-independent search engine like Google Scholar. Additionally, using keywords from the research questions, along with their synonyms, helps prevent capturing papers that rely on specific terminology. The goal is to ensure that the start set meets the following criteria: the papers should originate from different research groups to avoid clustering, and they should cover a diverse range of publishers, years, and authors.

Our previously identified set of secondary literature will serve as the start set, as it meets all relevant criteria. Most of this literature covers topics beyond the evaluation of code recommender systems. Therefore, we will only consider the references of the evaluation section in our snowballing process. One secondary study ([12]) does not state the references used for the evaluation section and will consequently be excluded from the initial set.

Since we are conducting a pilot search, only one iteration of the snowballing process will be performed.

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A total of 124 papers were identified through the backward snowballing process.

3. *Performing the literature review*: We combined the candidates from the automated search (27) and backward snowballing (124), resulting in an initial set of 151 studies. Since Google Scholar and the backward snowballing process do not allow automated metadata extraction, all post-processing and selection criteria evaluation steps were applied manually. The following post-processing steps were undertaken to refine this set:

- *Metadata processing*: The following metadata were extracted: Unique identifier (DOI), Authors, Title, Publication Year, Page Range, URL, Venue, Publisher.
- *Duplicate marking*: Duplicates were identified and removed based on titles, eliminating 15 duplicates.

In the next step the authors apply the selection criteria (see Section 6 and Section 6.4.1). The metadata-specific selection criteria are reviewed by the first author. The content-specific criteria are applied by three reviewers¹ (Sobernig, Innerebner, Borst) in two rounds. In the first round the authors screen the publications' titles, abstracts, keywords, and section headings. If necessary, the introduction and conclusion sections are also reviewed. In cases of disagreement, the authors reach a consensus during a second discussion round. Additional information on the selection criteria process can be found in Table 2.

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To evaluate the agreement among the three reviewers in applying the content-specific criteria, we calculated Krippendorff's Alpha ($\hat{\alpha}_c$) (see Section 6.5). The Krippendorff's Alpha among reviewers was $\hat{\alpha}_c = 0.45$. While below the conventional 0.67 threshold for tentative acceptability [25], this result is reasonable for a pilot study, as reviewers first needed to establish a common ground. The pilot thus fulfilled its role by highlighting ambiguities and informing refinements of the coding guidelines for the main study.

¹Throughout this work, any actions performed by individuals other than the author(s) or additional contributors are referred to as being conducted by *reviewers*.

Table 2: Summary of Selection Criteria Application to Publications Identified through Automated Search and Backward Snowballing.

Objective Selection Criteria	Number of Publications Not Fulfilling Criteria	Remaining Publications
Publication date	34	102
Page number	30	72
Full-text accesability	2	70
Publication language	0	70
Peer-reviewd	16	54
Primary study	5	49
Publication type	2	47
Originality	0	47
Subjective Selection Criteria	Number of Publications Not Fulfilling Criteria	Remaining Publications
Thematic relevance	22	25

4.2 Quasi-Gold Standard Corpus (QGS)

In this subsection, we follow the QGS guidelines proposed by Zhang et al. [5]. While drafting the protocol, we made two adaptations to better align with our research. First, rather than constructing the QGS based on specific publication venues, our method utilizes the publications identified during the pilot study, as they meet the key criteria of relevance, quality, and diversity. These criteria are ensured through a hybrid search strategy that combines a publisher-independent automated search with backward snowballing from secondary studies (see Section 4.1). Second, minimizing the number of search engines while covering the maximum number of venues with minimal overlap would limit our search to Scopus alone. However, we found that relying solely on one search engine, such as Scopus, could overly narrow our search scope. Additionally we noticed that Scopus does not fully cover certain important venues. Therefore, we chose to utilize multiple, overlapping search engines to ensure broader coverage, even if some duplication occurs. A detailed overview of the QGS publications is provided in Table 3.

Identify search engines: To identify the candidate search engines for the automated search, we base our selection on the venues of the QGS publications, following the criteria outlined below:

- For each publisher, an authoritative search engine is identified:

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The QGS publications originated from the following six publishers, listed in order of the number of venues: ACM (6 publication venues), IEEE (5), Elsevier (2), Springer (2), USENIX (1), and ACL (1). To cover these publishers, we selected the following four authoritative search engines, listed in the same order as above: ACMDL (ACM), IEEEExplore (IEEE), Scopus (Elsevier, USENIX, and ACL), and SpringerLink (Springer).

- The selection prioritizes engines that are accepted and widely used in primary SLRs within the field of software engineering [3].
- Preference is given to search engines that are publicly accessible to SE researchers, meaning those that do not require institutional subscriptions for access to search facilities. This approach facilitates the replication of automated searches in future studies. It is important to note that public access refers to search capabilities, not necessarily full-text access.
- If multiple engines cover the same venue, preference is given to the one with the most comprehensive time coverage.
- Zhang suggests to utilize a minimal number of search engines while covering the maximum number of venues with minimal overlap [5]:

Strictly following Zhang’s recommendation would limit our automated search to Scopus alone, as it covers all the venues and publications from the QGS corpus. However, we observed that Scopus lacks complete coverage for certain venues, such as ESEC. Additionally, because our search includes publications up to the search date, some recent publications from these venues may not yet be indexed in general databases like Scopus but are available in publisher-specific search engines like ACMDL, IEEEExplore, or SpringerLink (e.g., the SANER 2024 conference was not indexed in Scopus as of the investigation date, 07.08.24).

Relying solely on one search engine to minimize overlap could overly narrow our search, risking the exclusion of significant publications from venues not included in the QGS corpus. Therefore, we decided to use the following four search engines:

- ACM Digital Library (ACMDL)
- IEEEExplore
- SpringerLink
- Scopus

This approach aligns with the guidelines of Kitchenham and Brereton, who recommend using the digital libraries of at least two major publishers in software engineering (ACM, IEEE, and Springer) in combination with general indexing systems like Scopus [22]. To mitigate the risks associated with this unavoidable overlap, we conducted a thorough inspection of the automated search results to identify and remove duplicates (see Section 4.6).

Table 3: Summary of quasi-gold standard (QGS) publications, including their associated venues, publishers, and search engines.

Venue	Publisher	Publications	Engine
Conference proceedings			
SP	IEEE	[26]	IEEEExplore
USENIX Security Symposium	USENIX Association	[27]	Scopus
SCAM	IEEE	[28]	IEEEExplore
ICPC	ACM	[29]–[31]	ACMDL
EMNLP	Assoc. for Comput. Linguistics	[32]	Scopus
ICSE	ACM	[33]–[35]	ACMDL
SANER	IEEE	[36]	IEEEExplore
SLE	ACM	[1]	ACMDL
ASE	ACM	[37], [38]	ACMDL
ESEC	ACM	[39]	ACMDL
MSR	IEEE	[40]	IEEEExplore
BRACIS	Springer	[41]	SpringerLink
Journals			
Syst. Softw.	Elsevier	[42], [43]	Scopus
Vis. Lang. Comput.	Elsevier	[44]	Scopus
Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.	ACM	[45]	ACMDL
Trans. Software Eng.	IEEE	[46], [47]	IEEEExplore
Empir. Softw. Eng.	Springer	[48], [49]	SpringerLink

Figure 1: Euler diagram illustrating the overlap of QGS publications across different search engines.

4.3 Defining and Refining Search Terms

In line with Zhang’s guidelines, we adopt a QGS-based approach for search term elicitation, using the publications from the QGS corpus to minimize author bias. We follow Zhang’s subjective search string definition approach, as it allows us to use our domain knowledge and insights from the pilot study to refine the search string. For this process, we manually extract candidate search terms by analyzing the titles, abstracts, and keywords of all QGS publications. Additionally, we incorporate terms derived from our research questions (see Section 2).

V. 3

The following candidate search terms were extracted from the titles, abstracts, and keywords of the QGS publications:

- [26] *Assessing^e, GitHub Copilot^t’s^t, AI pair programmer^t, code generation^a*
- [27] *User Study, Large Language Model Code Assistants, OpenAI Codex^t, AI-based coding assistants, assess^e, programmers^s*
- [49] *GitHub’s Copilot^t, software development^s, software engineering^s, generated code, study^e*
- [28] *Empirical Study, Code Generation^a, study^e, source code generation tool, code generation technique, Transformer-based Code Generation, GitHub copilot^t*
- [29] *Code Comment Generation^a, software maintenance^a, developers^s, comments generation, experiments^e, evaluate^e, program comprehension^a*
- [32] *Context-based Code Generation, code generation^a, contextual code generation, Experiments^e, code generation models*
- [33] *Software testing^a, software developers^s, automate software testing, code completion^a, recommended assert statements^a*
- [30] *Code Summarization^a, Automatic source code summarization, automatic code summarization, evaluate^e, software engineering^s*
- [47] *evaluate^e, evaluation^e, bug fixing^a, bug fix pattern, code synthesis^a, empirical software engineering*

[31] software *maintenance*^a, ~~automatic comment generation~~, *evaluate*^e, *experiments*^e, Software *maintenance*^a, ~~Documentation~~, Code comment *generation*^a

[36] *Validation*^e, *evaluation*^e, ~~Maintenance~~, Model Driven *Engineering*^s, Software *Engineering*^s, language *workbenches*^t

[50] ~~recommender systems~~, *recommender*^t, Software *Engineering*^s, ~~evaluation metrics~~, *assess*^e, ~~case study~~, ~~offline experiment~~, modelling *chatbot*^t

[37] ~~Static Type Recommendation~~, program *documentation*^a, *evaluate*^e, type *recommendation*^a, static *analysis*^a

[46] Refactoring *Recommendations*^a, ~~Maintenance~~, ~~Search-based software engineering~~, *Refactoring*^a

[44] *Evaluation*^e, ~~Multi-Recommendation System~~, software *maintenance*^a, query *recommendation*^a, *evaluated*^e, field *study*, ~~Recommender systems~~

[43] ~~Recommendation system~~, code *completion*^a, ~~recommendations~~, ~~code completion mechanisms~~, *evaluated*^e

[42] GitHub *Copilot*^t, AI pair *programmer*^t, Automatic program *synthesis*^a, software *engineering*^s, *Copilot*^t, *studies*^e, *evaluate*^e, ~~empirical evaluations~~, computer *science*^s, Code *completion*^a, ~~Testing~~

[34] Code *Generation*^a, ~~Empirical Study~~, GitHub *Copilot*^t, Software *engineering*^s, code *completion*^a, deep learning-based code generators

[45] *Evaluation*^e, Code Documentation *Generation*^a, ~~Automatic code documentation generation~~, software *engineering*^s, ~~code documentation~~, *experiments*^e, code comment *generation*^a, commit message *generation*^a

[39] Code *Generation*^a, software *development*^s, code *completion*^a, ~~code completion tool~~

[38] Code *Generation*^a, ~~Automated code generation~~, import *generation*^a, *evaluate*^e, *experiments*^e, software *development*^s, ~~Surveys~~, Task *analysis*^a

[48] ~~Code-example recommender~~, *evaluate*^e, *validate*^e, Code *recommendation*^a

[35] Code *Completion*^a, ~~Case Study~~, ~~completion tools~~, software *developer*^s, ~~neural machine translation model~~

[40] Neural Code Completion, Code *completion*^a, *evaluate*^e, neural framework for code completion

[41] software *development*^s, code *intelligence*^a, code *completion*^a, *study*^e, *evaluation*^e, *experiments*^e

After merging the search terms from the QGS publications with those from the research questions, data cleansing was performed through the following steps:

- Removal of duplicates (strikethrough)
- Removal of redundant terms (strikethrough)
- Conversion of plural to singular forms
- Addition of alternative noun forms for gerunds
- Conversion of uppercase to lowercase writing
- Addition of alternative BE/AE spellings of a word

We build on the search term categories identified during the pilot search. Instead of using two separate search strings as in the pilot search, we merge these categories into a single search string that includes the following categories: (*evaluation*^e), (*software engineering*^s), (*tool*^t), and (*action*^a) (see Section 4.1). Within each category, terms are linked by the OR operator, while the categories themselves are connected using the AND operator.

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Listing 3: The initial search string.

```
("evaluat*" OR "assess*" OR "study" OR "experiment") AND ("github copilot" OR "ai pair programmer" OR "recommender" OR "code assistant" OR "openai codex" OR "language workbench" OR "modelling chatbot") AND ("software engineering" OR "software development" OR "computer science" OR "programming" OR "model-driven engineering" OR "model driven engineering" OR "MDE") AND ("query recommendation" OR "code completion" OR "code intelligence" OR "code recommendation" OR "refactoring recommendation" OR "code generation" OR "task analysis" OR "import generation" OR "code comment generation" OR "code documentation generation" OR "automatic program synthesis" OR "commit message generation" OR "software maintenance" OR "refactoring" OR "static analysis" OR "type inference" OR "type recommendation" OR "program documentation" OR "program comprehension" OR "software testing" OR "assert statement recommendation" OR "code summarization" OR "code summarisation" OR "bug fixing" OR "code synthesis")
```

The initial search string is constructed from four categories: evaluation, software engineering, tool, and actions. It contains 43 distinct search terms, leading to 4900 unique search quadruplets.

Using the above search string resulted in a quasi-sensitivity level of 0.12% [5]; that is, 3 out of 25 QGS publications are contained by the set of 319 total search hits.

We continuously assess the performance of the search string by calculating the quasi-sensitivity across all selected engines. The Quasi-sensitivity is defined as the proportion of relevant papers (QGS papers) retrieved by an automated search relative to the size of the QGS corpus. The goal is to attain a quasi-sensitivity level of at least 70% to 80%, with higher values being preferable (see Section 4.6).

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Insights gained from repeated evaluations of the initial search string using quasi-sensitivity led to changes aimed at maximizing QGS coverage and reducing the number of thematically irrelevant search hits:

- The search was limited to Abstract, Title, and Keywords instead of all fields to increase relevance.
- We removed the category (*software engineering*^s) as it was observed that these terms are often not mentioned in the titles, abstracts, or keywords of QGS publications.
- We merged the categories (*tool*^t) and (*action*^a), as many QGS publications only mention terms belonging to one of these categories.
- The removal of the "software engineering" category resulted in a significant increase in search hits (76390), as search terms from the categories "action" and "tool" are also widely used in other subject areas, now yielding results in those areas. The following search terms were identified, with single terms resulting in a search hit increase of 1000 or above being removed. The other subject areas related to these terms are indicated in brackets:
 - "recommender": Search hit increase 27174 (engineering, mathematics)
 - "task analysis": Search hit increase 23033 (social science, medicine)
 - "static analysis": Search hit increase 15227 (engineering, material science)
 - "program comprehension": Search hit increase 1423 (social science, physics)

- "program documentation": Search hit increase 1765 (engineering, medicine)
- Merging the "action" and "tool" categories similarly caused a significant increase in search hits (12218), as terms from the action category, which were previously in combination with terms from the tool category specific to code recommender systems, no longer directly applied to this domain. The following search terms were identified, with single terms resulting in a search hit increase of 3000 or above being removed:
 - "software testing": Search hit increase 50204
 - "software maintenance": Search hit increase 6663
 - "refactoring": Search hit increase 3380

Listing 4: The final search string used for the automated search.

```
("evaluat*" OR "assess*" OR "study" OR "experiment") AND ("github copilot" OR "ai pair programmer" OR "code assistant" OR "openai codex" OR "query recommendation" OR "code completion" OR "code intelligence" OR "code recommendation" OR "refactoring recommendation" OR "code generation" OR "import generation" OR "commit message generation" OR "code comment generation" OR "code documentation generation" OR "automatic program synthesis" OR "assert statement recommendation" OR "code summarization" OR "code summarisation" OR "language workbench" OR "bug fixing" OR "type recommendation" OR "modelling chatbot" OR "code synthesis")
```

The final search string is built from the two categories evaluation and tool&action. It includes 27 different search terms, resulting in 92 unique search pairs.

Using the updated search string resulted in a quasi-sensitivity level of 0.96% [5]; that is, 24 out of 25 QGS publications are contained by the set of 4,101 total search hits. See also Section 4.6.

4.4 Assessing Engine Capabilities

To ensure an effective and efficient search procedure using the selected search engines (see Section 4.2), we will first assess the capabilities of each engine. This assessment will involve evaluating the following aspects for each search engine:

1. *Search Site*: The URL of the search site is documented for reference.
2. *Support for Complex Queries*: The engine supports complex query structures, including nested Boolean expressions and the use of metadata fields.
3. *Full-Text Indexing*: The engine indexes the full text of publications, rather than merely providing access to the full text.
4. *Abstract Indexing*: The engine indexes the abstracts of publications, allowing queries to be evaluated against abstract texts and enabling search restrictions to abstracts.
5. *Title Indexing*: The engine indexes the titles of publications, allowing queries to be evaluated against title texts and enabling searches to be restricted to titles.
6. *Keyword Indexing*: The engine indexes author-provided keywords, allowing queries to be evaluated against keywords and enabling searches to be restricted to keywords.
7. *Language Support*: The engine contains publications in languages other than English, indicating that the full-text language may not be English.
8. *Date Range Restriction*: The engine allows the search to be restricted to specific ranges of publication years.
9. *Venue Type Restriction*: The engine allows the search to be restricted to specific venue types, such as conferences or journals.

10. *Per-Query Restrictions*: The engine imposes certain limitations on individual queries, such as capped result sets or a limited number of expression components.
11. *Result Set Ordering*: The engine allows control over the ordering of the result set, such as sorting by relevance or publication date.
12. *Output Format Control*: The engine allows control over the output format of result sets.
13. *Reference List Exporting*: The engine allows for exporting the reference lists of individual search hits or publications.

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The capabilities and restrictions of the selected search engines are summarized in Table 4. The key findings from our assessment are as follows:

1. We consulted the following search sites for the selected engines:
 - ACMDL *Advanced Search*: <https://dl.acm.org/search/advanced>
 - IEEEEXplore *Command Search*: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/search/advanced/command>
 - Scopus *Advanced Search*: <https://www.scopus.com/search/form.uri?display=advanced>
 - SpringerLink *Advanced Search*: <https://link.springer.com/advanced-search>
2. All four search engines support the use of complex, nested search expressions using Boolean operators. This capability allowed us to execute single, comprehensive searches across ACMDL, IEEEEXplore, SpringerLink, and Scopus without needing to decompose the search string into smaller sub-queries.
3. ACMDL, IEEEEXplore, and SpringerLink index the full text of publications, while Scopus operates primarily as a bibliographic search engine.
- (4-6) The engines: ACMDL, IEEEEXplore, and Scopus, provide access to key metadata fields, including publication titles, abstracts, and author-provided keywords. While SpringerLink offers access to publication titles, it does not provide access to abstracts or author-provided keywords. It's important to note that in our context, "accessibility" refers to having control over this metadata. SpringerLink may include abstracts and author keywords in its search evaluation, but this behavior cannot be controlled by the reviewer. The ability to control searches using these metadata fields varies slightly:
 - ACMDL allows metadata-specific restrictions via a web form or by using metadata prefixes in Boolean queries (e.g., "Abstract":"term").
 - IEEEEXplore offers prefixes in its Command Search (e.g., "Abstract":"term").
 - Scopus defaults to searching within titles, abstracts, and keywords in its advanced search mode, including both author-provided and publisher-provided keywords.
 - SpringerLink does not allow for limiting searches to all three metadata fields.

For ACMDL and IEEEEXplore we opted for the the prefix annotation. For scopus we applied the metadata restrictions using the advanced search mode. For SpringerLink control over the search results in this respect was not possible.
- (7) ACMDL and IEEEEXplore only index publications with English full texts, whereas SpringerLink and Scopus may also return non-English publications, provided they include an English abstract. To ensure consistency, we added language constraints to the SpringerLink and Scopus queries using a dedicated metadata field or filter.

- (8) All four search engines support queries restricted to specific publication years (2017–2024), and our search implementations were adjusted to include these constraints.
- (9) To target the relevant venue types (see Section 6): archival venues (journals) and presence venues (conferences), each engine offers specific filtering options:

- ACMDL allows restrictions to journals, proceedings (including workshops), and newsletters via its web UI.
- IEEEExplore enables filtering for "Conferences," "Magazines," and "Journals" through its UI.
- Scopus uses metadata annotations (field code DOCTYPE) to restrict searches to specific venue types (e.g., "ar" for journal articles, "cp" for conference proceedings).
- SpringerLink allows filtering by different publication types (e.g., book chapters, articles); however, these Springer-specific categories did not align with our categorization. Therefore, we did not apply this filter.

We applied the filters to our search implementation.

- (10) Each engine presents unique challenges regarding query and result-set extraction:

- ACMDL imposes no significant restrictions on query length (e.g., clauses, terms) or on the nesting depth which would apply to our generic search string. There was no general capping on result-set extraction.
- IEEEExplore Command Search announces a maximum of 25 search terms per search clause, however our generic search string (which counted more than 25 search terms being connected by boolean operators) was accepted and processed. IEEEExplore has a download cap of 1,000 search hits.
- Scopus did not impose any actual restrictions on query length or nesting depth. The result-set extraction allowed a maximum of 20,000 search hits to be exported.
- SpringerLink allows the extraction of a maximum of 1,000 search hits. Moreover, the data extracted from SpringerLink does not include the metadata fields: page number, publisher, and keywords.

- (11) All engines provide options for ordering search results, including by relevance, publication year, author, and recency. We prioritized relevance-based ordering during searches to optimize results within the export limits imposed by some engines.

- (12) The engines offer various output formats:

- ACMDL offers only bibliographic database format representations (BibTeX, EndNote, ACM Ref)
- IEEEExplore provide plain text, bibliographic database formats (BibTeX, RIS, RefWorks), and a comma-separated value list representation (CSV).
- Scopus likewise allowed plain text, bibliographic database formats (BibTeX, RIS), and a comma-separated value list representation (CSV).
- SpringerLink offers only a comma-separated value list representation (CSV).

For IEEEExplore, SpringerLink, and Scopus, we opted for the CSV format because this representation can easily be processed and converted in a spreadsheet (for the review and selection phase). For ACMDL, we chose the BibTeX format and later converted it into a CSV file.

- (13) None of the search engines allow for exporting reference lists of individual publications in a processable format. For the backward snowballing step (see Section 5), we manually extracted reference lists from the markup records of papers identified during the main search, compiling them into a spreadsheet for further review.

Table 4: Overview of capabilities and restrictions of each search engine.

Search Engine	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
ACMDL	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	no	yes	partly yes (only bibliographic database format representations: BibTeX, EndNote, ACM Ref)	no
IEEEExplore	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes (25 search terms, export of 1000 results max.)	yes	yes (CSV, BibTeX, RIS, RefWorks)	no
Scopus	yes	no	yes (export of 20000 results max.)	yes	yes (CSV, BibTeX, RIS)	no						
SpringerLink	yes	yes	no	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes (export of 10000 results max.; metadata fields: page number, publisher, keywords not extractable)	yes	yes (CSV)	no

4.5 Performing Engine Searches

The defined search string will be adapted to the restrictions and capabilities of each search engine. This adaptation involves adjusting syntax and operators to align with each search engine’s requirements. For instance, incorporating syntax for constraints over metadata fields, like specifying publication language or applying time-range restrictions, where applicable. The resulting, engine-specific search strings will be documented as follows:

- Exact search string:

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The exact search strings for the four search engines are listed in the Appendix; see Section B.

- Date of running the search:

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- ACMDL: Nov. 4, 2024;
- IEEEExplore: Nov. 4, 2024;
- Scopus: Nov. 4, 2024;
- SpringerLink: Nov. 4, 2024;

- Number of search hits:

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In total, we obtained a result set of 4,101 publications from the four search engines (see also Table 9)

- ACMDL: 347 (uncapped exports, equals total hits)
- IEEEExplore: 752 (uncapped exports, equals total hits)
- Scopus: 2,694 (uncapped exports, equals total hits)
- SpringerLink: 308 (uncapped exports, equals total hits)

- Adaptions to the basic search string, required by a search-engine’s capabilities:

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We modified the engine-specific implementations as follows:

- ACMDL:
 - * (Result page) Setting **Publication Date** to **2017-2024**;
- IEEEExplore:
 - * (Result page) Setting **Year Range** to **2017-2025**;
 - * (Result page) For **Content Type** ticking **Conferences** and **Journals**;
- Scopus:
 - * Adding a clause of two metadata terms **PUBYEAR** > / < **yyyy** to limit the search to the review years: **AND PUBYEAR > 2016 AND PUBYEAR < 2026**;
 - * Adding a clause of one metadata term **LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA, value: (LIMIT-TO(SUBJAREA,"COMP"))**) ;
 - * Adding a clause of two metadata terms **LIMIT-TO(DOCTYPE, value: (LIMIT-TO(DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar"))**);
 - * Adding a clause of one metadata term **LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, value: (LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE,"English"))**);
 - * Adding a clause of two metadata terms **LIMIT-TO(SRCTYPE, value: (LIMIT-TO(SRCTYPE,"p") OR LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE,"j"))**);
- SpringerLink:
 - * Adding a filter to limit the search to the review years: *ifpub_year.isdigit()and2017 <= int(pub_year) <= 2025* :
 - * Adding a filter to restrict results to English full-text publications: *iflanguage == 'en'* :

- Specific conditions for each search:

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The search on SpringerLink was scripted using the Springer Nature API, allowing the application of the search string across the Title, Abstract, and Keywords fields and enabling the extraction of all relevant metadata from the publications. For the remaining three engines, we instrumented the browser and web UI of the respective engines.

4.6 Post-processing Result Sets

Automated metadata extraction: To prepare the publications for further review, the following operations are performed on the bibliographical metadata:

- Using the selected search engines (see Section 4.2), the following metadata entries can be automatically retrieved: Unique identifier (DOI), Authors, Title, Publication Year, Page Range, URL, Publisher, Abstract, and Keywords (see also Section 7).

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The criteria used to extract key metadata fields from the four resulting datasets, as required by Section 7, are documented in Table 6. For datasets missing certain metadata (page range and Keywords), reviewers accessed this information through external resources identifiable by the DOI or URL, rather than replicating the metadata directly.

- The metadata fields for search engine and search datetime are automatically added to each corresponding metadata set.

- Any metadata fields that remain incomplete after the process, particularly those not fully supported by search engines (e.g., Venue), will be manually completed by consulting external resources identified through the DOI or URL.

Automated duplicate detection: Duplicate publications (referred to as "duplicates" hereafter) are identified and either removed automatically or marked through a series of incremental steps. A duplicate is defined as the repeated occurrence of the same publication within a single result set (intra-source duplicate) or across multiple result sets (inter-source duplicate). The detection process first addresses intra-source duplicates, followed by inter-source duplicates. The operations are performed in the following order:

- Matching DOIs: DOIs are compared, and duplicates are automatically removed when matched.

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Of the total search hits, 92% (3,760) included a DOI. SpringerLink provided complete DOI coverage, while ACM DL covered 99% (343/347), IEEE Xplore covered 93% (700/752) and Scopus covered 89% (2,409/2,694) (see Table 9).

For publications without DOIs, additional steps are employed to detect duplicates using other metadata fields:

- Matching Publication Titles:
 - All publication titles are standardized into a unique, canonical form by tokenizing the text, removing punctuation, special characters, and symbols, eliminating white spaces, and converting all characters to lowercase.
 - Publications with identical titles are printed (including metadata fields: search engine, authors, publisher, venue), manually reviewed, and in case of duplication removed.

V. 8

The findings of the duplicate-detection step were the following (see Table 9):

- *Intra-source duplicates*
 - ACM DL, IEEE Xplore, and SpringerLink contained no identifiable duplicates at this stage, regardless of the detection strategy applied.
 - For Scopus, a total of 11 intra-source duplicates were identified: nine based on DOIs and an additional two through title matching.
- *Inter-source duplicates*
 - In total, we identified 967 unique DOIs with at least one occurrence in multiple result sets: 906 appeared in two result sets, and 61 appeared in three result sets.
 - Among its total DOIs, ACM DL contained 83% non-unique DOIs (284 out of 347), IEEE Xplore 90% (632 out of 752), Scopus 40% (965 out of 2,409), and SpringerLink 37% (114 out of 308).
 - Examining pairs of result sets, the highest DOI overlap was 18%, observed between IEEE Xplore and Scopus, followed by 9.3% between ACM DL and Scopus (see Table 7).
 - Among the remaining records without a DOI, we found two instances of non-unique titles, with overlap occurring between ACM DL and Scopus, as well as between IEEE Xplore and Scopus (see Table 8).

The removal procedure was conducted as follows:

- The result sets were ordered in this sequence: SpringerLink, ACMDL, IEEEExplore, Scopus.
- When duplicates appeared in multiple result sets, the entry from the earliest result set in the list was retained, and duplicates were removed from result sets appearing later in the list.
- This ordering ensures that publications from a publisher’s search engine are preserved within its corresponding result set. SpringerLink is prioritized as it exclusively indexes Springer publications, while Scopus is placed last due to its indexing of publications from ACM, IEEE, and Springer.
- After completing automated duplicate detection and manually filling in missing metadata fields, an additional semi-automated duplicate detection step was conducted, including the following steps:
 - DOIs are compared using excel, and duplicates are manually removed when matched.
 - Publication titles are compared using excel, and duplicates are manually removed when matched.

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- *Overall automated duplicate removal:* Based on these findings, we removed 1,042 duplicate hits, representing 25% of the total search hits across all four result sets.
- The highest number of duplicates was found, verified, and removed from Scopus: 978 duplicates, or 36% (978 out of 2,694). Scopus was followed by IEEEExplore with an 8% duplicate rate (63 out of 752).
- This finding aligns with our initial expectations regarding the overlap between Scopus and the other three engines, as discussed earlier (see Section 4.2).
- Limitations of the automated duplicate detection procedure:
 - *Metadata Quality:* We encountered several metadata issues that impacted the effectiveness of both automated duplicate detection strategies (DOI, title matching):
 - * *Mistyped or Inconsistent DOIs:* We identified mistyped DOIs (e.g., with a dash instead of an underscore) and different DOIs referring to the same publication. Such inconsistencies can lead to missed duplicates in DOI-based detection.
 - * *Title Encoding Errors:* Character-set encoding issues affected title matching, with special characters occasionally converted to alternate encodings. We identified several cases involving different dash and wildcard characters.
 - *Title Ambiguity:* Title matching is a weak indicator due to the possibility of identical titles in follow-up publications by the same authors or other nuanced cases. Although manual review helped to address these ambiguities, it required considerable effort.
- As a result, we identified another 56 duplicates (1 from ACMDL, 31 from IEEEExplore, and 24 from Scopus) during the selection semi-automated duplicate detection procedure. Consequently, the authoritative combined dataset for the actual selection phase included 3,003 publications.

Sensitivity analysis: Quasi-sensitivity is defined as the proportion of relevant papers (QGS papers) retrieved by an automated search relative to the size of the QGS corpus. A quasi-sensitivity level between 70% and 80% is considered acceptable[5].

To assess this, we will compute several statistics:

- **Quasi-Sensitivity Ratio per Engine/Result Set:** This measures the number of QGS publications expected to be retrieved by a specific search engine (based on its publisher; see **Table 5**) compared to the actual number of QGS publications retrieved from that engine.

V. 8

The raw data is summarized in Table 10 columns 1 (expected) and 2 (intra-source):

- The result set retrieved from ACMDL contained five of the 11 expected QGS publications (quasi-sensitivity ratio of 0.45).
- The result set retrieved from IEEEExplore contained all of the six expected QGS publications (quasi-sensitivity ratio of 1).
- The result set retrieved from Scopus contained all out of five expected QGS publications (quasi-sensitivity ratio of 1).
- The result set retrieved from SpringerLink contained two out of the three expected QGS publications (quasi-sensitivity ratio of 0.66).

- **Quasi-Sensitivity Ratio Across All Engines/Result Sets:** This is the ratio of the total number of QGS publications retrieved from all selected search engines to the total number of QGS publications (refer to Section 4.2).

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- The total, unique search hits retrieved from all four search engines (4,101) contained 24 (i.e., sum of column 2, intra-source, of Table 10). out of 25 QGS publications. This yields a quasi-sensitivity ratio of 0.96.
- More than 80% of the expected QGS publications linked to ACMDL, IEEEExplore, Scopus, and SpringerLink could be found either in the respective engine itself or any of the other engines (inter-source)

5 Snowballing Strategy

To ensure that our paper corpus represents a comprehensive selection of relevant literature, we will utilize backward snowballing (citation-based search) in accordance with the guidelines outlined by Wohlin [4], including the following steps:

1. *Identifying a start set:* The process begins by identifying a start set of papers, which will serve as the basis for reference extraction. These papers must meet the selection criteria outlined in Section 6, with efforts made to minimize author bias during the selection process. Therefore the start set will consist of papers that were ultimately included from the automated search step.
2. *Iterations:* Once the start set is established, we will initiate a series of iterations to identify relevant prior work by examining the references cited within the start set. The first iteration will focus on these initial papers, while subsequent iterations will build on papers selected in previous rounds. This iterative process will continue until no new relevant papers are identified.
3. *Reference extraction:* For the start set, references will be extracted using digital library capabilities, while subsequent iterations will involve manual extraction using a spreadsheet (see Section 7). The essential information required for each reference includes the publication title, publication venue, and a list of authors.
4. *Post-processing:* Candidate papers identified in each iteration will undergo post-processing, including a duplicate check using the procedure outlined in Section 4.6.
5. *Selection:* The remaining references will be assessed against the selection criteria in Section 6.
6. *Quality assessment:* Papers that meet the selection criteria will be subjected to a thorough quality assessment, following the procedures defined in Section 6.3.

7. *Data extraction*: Finally, papers that pass all selection and quality assessment criteria will undergo a decision-data extraction process as described in Section 7. These included papers will then form the start set for the next iteration, continuing the cycle until the corpus is fully developed.

V. 9

Snowballing was not performed, as the automated search already yielded a sufficient number of relevant publications. Snowballing may, however, be considered at a later stage if required to complement the identified corpus.

6 Selection Criteria

6.1 Inclusion and Exclusion

We implement two distinct types of selection criteria: metadata-specific and content-specific. The metadata-specific criteria are to be assessed first, as they can be efficiently verified against a predefined checklist, allowing for a straightforward filtering of studies. Only publications that satisfy all metadata-specific criteria proceed to the next stage, where content-specific criteria are applied. The sequence of criteria application within each set of criteria is informed by insights from the pilot study. This approach prioritizes easily verifiable criteria, reserving more complex, in-depth content analyses for later stages in the evaluation process.

The metadata-specific criteria are applied in the following order:

C₁ Publication date: The publication must not be published before 2017. The period from 2017 onwards marks an important era in the field of code recommender systems (see Figure 2). Advancements in this domain during that period, particularly with the introduction and refinement of code embeddings and transformer-based models, have led to more powerful tools, such as AI-powered systems like GitHub Copilot, which have significantly enhanced the performance and capabilities of code recommender systems. This progress has heightened interest in these systems as they become increasingly popular in software engineering practice [23]. Given this context, starting the literature review from 2017 ensures a focus on contemporary and impactful research that leverages the latest technological advancements. Work published until the day of the search Nov., 2024 is included in the systematic review.

C₂ Page number: Publications must have a minimum of eight pages. This criterion helps avoid the inclusion of short papers, workshop papers, position papers, and notes on posters, talks, tutorials, and tool demonstrations, which often lack the space for a detailed methodology and thorough discussion. These shorter formats typically do not provide the necessary depth and rigor needed for comprehensive evaluation. By focusing on full research papers, we aim to maintain consistency across the studies reviewed, ensuring that each contributes meaningfully and substantially to our analysis. The eight-page threshold was chosen because major conferences in the domain, such as ICSE and ASE, typically allow full research papers up to 12 pages, with some extending even further (e.g., CHI, ESEC).

C₃ Full-text accessibility: The full text of the publication must be accessible to the authors, either through the publisher’s digital libraries (provided the authors or their institutions have the necessary subscriptions), the author’s personal webpage, or third-party online platforms such as Citeseer.

V. 10

Out of 4,101 unique search results (see Section 4.6), 177 publications were not accessible to the authors and were thus excluded (0 from ACM DL, 41 from IEEE Xplore, 82 from Scopus, and 54 from SpringerLink).

C₄ Publication language: The full text of the publication must be written in English or have an available and accessible English version. Just having an English title, abstract, keywords, or other metadata is not sufficient.

C₅ Peer-reviewed: A peer-review process must be established for a publication’s venue to ensure the inclusion of mature and rigorous research content.

C₆ Primary study: Only primary studies will be included in this review. Any other forms of research, such as secondary or tertiary studies, will be excluded.

C₇ Publication type: A publication must be published as a full research paper or a special-issue research paper in a journal venue. This excludes article types such as workshop papers, editorials, columns, book chapters, and technical reports. For archival venues, formats other than periodicals, such as monographs, article collections, or research reports, are also excluded. Additionally, publications will be excluded if they were not presented as full research papers in a presence venue, which means that short papers, position papers, and notes on posters, talks, tutorials, and tool demonstrations are also excluded.

C₈ Originality: Extensions or follow-up publications are excluded if the corresponding original work is already included in the publication corpus but was excluded during selection or quality assessment. If both the original and its extension pass the selection criteria and quality assessment, they are merged and treated as a single publication from the point of identification. If the original is not included in the corpus but an extension or follow-up publication passes all selection criteria, the original is regarded as an accessible research artifact and considered together with the extension in all further steps.

The content-specific criteria are applied in the following order:

- **C₉ Context:** A publication must explicitly address systems and operations that support software engineering activities related to the process of creating or modifying software language code (see Section 2). Relevance is determined by the authors through an assessment of the title, keywords, and abstract. A publication is to be excluded if it meets one or both of the following conditions:
 - *Non-Computer Science Subject Area:* The publication focuses on a subject area unrelated to Computer Science. If multiple subject areas apply and one of them is Computer Science, the publication is included. If excluded, the subject area is documented using the following categories [51]: Arts and Humanities [AH]; Biology and Life Sciences [BL]; Business, Economics, and Management [BEM]; Chemistry and Material Sciences [CM]; Mathematics [M]; Engineering [E]; Environmental and Earth Sciences [EE]; Medicine and Pharmacology [MP]; Physical Sciences [PS]; Public Health and Healthcare [PH]; Social Sciences [SS]; Other [O].
 - *Non-Code Artifact Type:* The artifact investigated in the publication is not related to code following the software language definition (see Section 7.1 D5). If multiple artifact types are investigated and one of them includes Code, the publication will be included. The following artifact types, derived from Pfeiffer [52] and Lúcio et al. [53], are considered and to be documented (a full list with subcategories and examples is provided in the appendix; see Table 14): Code, Data, Documentation, or Other.

V. 10

In total 475 publications were excluded based on selection criterion C9. A detailed overview of the exclusion reasons and investigated artifact types is provided in Figure 5 and Figure 14.

- **C₁₀ Thematic relevance:** Publications must be thematically relevant to the SLR. Each publication is assessed based on its title, abstract, keywords, and section headings. If there is any doubt, the introduction and conclusion are also reviewed. Three authors independently evaluate all publications, rating their thematic relevance on the following scale:

- *Not Relevant*: The paper does not address code recommender systems² (method, technique, tool) in software development or their evaluation³ (utterly unrelated to the topic).
- *Slightly Relevant*: The paper mentions code recommender systems (method, technique, tool) in software development as a minor contribution, but the main focus is on a different topic. An evaluation is not documented.
- *Moderately Relevant*: The paper mentions code recommender systems (method, technique, tool) in software development and their evaluation as minor contributions, but the main focus is on a different topic.
- *Relevant*: The paper addresses code recommender systems (method, technique, tool) in software development as its major contribution, a report on the evaluation is the minor contribution.
- *Highly Relevant*: The paper directly addresses the evaluation of code recommender systems in software development as a major contribution. Still, the report on the code recommender system (method, technique, tool) itself is a minor one.

V. 11

An example illustrating the application of criterion C10 is publication SPR173 [54]. Based on the title, abstract, and keywords, the publication initially appeared to report a user study evaluating a CRS and was therefore rated as "Relevant". However, the full-text review (during data extraction) revealed that participants perform debugging tests before and after interacting with the CRS, while no interaction with the CRS is allowed during the tests themselves. Consequently, the study does not directly evaluate the CRS, and the publication is considered not relevant.

Disagreements are resolved through a consensus reached in a second discussion round. Only papers rated as "Relevant" or "Highly Relevant" are included in the review.

V. 8

The original procedure for C3 required substantial effort, as it involved manually accessing each publication through publisher platforms. This was necessary because search engines do not offer automated full-text extraction and prohibit web scraping, making the process time-consuming and labor-intensive. To address this challenge, we incorporated the APIs of Open Access Button^a and Unpaywall^b. These tools automate the verification of legal full-text availability and provide URLs when accessible. Additionally, full-text downloads were deferred to after C9, as C10 requires full-text access for evaluation.

^a<https://openaccessbutton.org/>

^b<https://unpaywall.org/>

V. 9

While all included publications (rated as "Relevant" or "Highly Relevant") were considered for the data analysis of RQ1, the analyses for RQ2–RQ4 were planned in two rounds. In the first round, we considered only those publications that received a "Highly Relevant" rating by at least one reviewer and remained included in case of disagreement. The first analysis round includes a total of 92 publications (see Table 15). Focusing on this subset ensured that the first round captured publications making a major contribution to the evaluation of code recommender systems, which we expected to provide the

²Definition code recommender system: A system that provides a programmer with automatically generated recommendations within the context of programming-language services, encompassing both syntactic aspects like static program analysis and semantic aspects such as automated code generation, aimed at enhancing work practices and outcomes. This system operates on code, requiring that either its input or output is a code artifact. (see Table 14 and Section 7.1).

³Definition Evaluation: Systematic determination of an artifact's quality typically involving an additional data source such as human participants. It often includes validation to ensure the artifact functions correctly before assessing its impact in context.

richest data. This staged approach allows us to first analyze the most information-rich studies in depth before extending the analysis to the broader set of included publications in the planned second round.

Figure 2: Timeline showing recent technological advancements in the code recommender system domain [23].

6.2 Selection States

During the selection process, as documented in Section 6.1, each publication under review passes through several intermediate selection states before reaching a final decision state: either excluded or included. The selection process involves two main evaluation steps:

1. *Metadata-specific Criteria Evaluation:* If any of the objective criteria (C1–C8) is not met, the publication is excluded and marked as Not Matching the Metadata-specific Criteria (NMMC).
2. *Content-specific Criteria Evaluation:* If the publication has not already been excluded and fails to meet the content-specific criteria (C9–C10), it is excluded and classified as Off Topic (OT).

For documentation and analysis purposes, the final selection states: Included, Excluded (NMMC), and Excluded (OT), are recorded (see also Section 7).

V. 10

Table 11 summarizes the number of publications excluded during the selection process, categorized by the reasons for exclusion (see also Figure 3).

6.3 Quality Assessment

To ensure the quality of the publications selected as inclusion candidates (see Section 6), we conducted a quality assessment focusing on two key aspects: 1) duplicate publications and 2) the correctness of the evaluation documentation.

Figure 3: Number of publications identified per search engine/method, stacked by category: QGS publications in included publications, included publications, duplicates, and excluded publications. The x-axis uses a compressed, nonlinear scale to enhance visibility of both small and large counts.

- *Duplicates*: While the automated duplicate-detection process during data cleansing is effective, it may occasionally overlook duplicates. This can occur, for example, when identical publications are listed under different DOIs due to parallel publishing channels for proceedings articles, or when variations in title formatting obscure duplicates. To mitigate these risks, we manually review the selected publications during the quality assessment phase, specifically checking for any duplicates that the automated process might have missed.

V. 10

Among the candidate publications from the main search, two previously undetected duplicates were identified and removed from the Scopus set.

- *Documentation*: The publications ultimately included in our review (see Section 6) undergo an assessment of the level of documentation. Reviewers evaluate the completeness of study setup details, including artifacts, participants, and evaluation metrics, following the order outlined below. Any publication that receives a rating below *Documented* in the artifacts field or below *Partly Documented* in either the participants or evaluation metrics fields is marked as ERRoneous (ERR) and excluded from further review. If the participants field is rated *No Participants Involved*, this criterion is disregarded for the exclusion decision. In cases of doubt or unresolved disagreement between the two independent reviewers (see Section 7.2), the publication will be excluded. This step is essential to ensure that only methodologically sound and repeatable studies are included.

Based on relevant literature (e.g., [3], [55], [56]) and insights from our pilot study, we will assess the included publications for the following types of quality criteria:

- External Source: A collection of supplementary artifacts to replicate a study including material archives, publication supplements, and other publications.
 - * *Yes*: At least one external source is provided.
 - * *No*: No external source is provided.
- Research Artifacts:
 - * *Definition*:

- *Experimental Design & Protocol*: The study’s design (objectives, variables, hypotheses) and protocol (procedures, timelines).
- *Experimental Materials*: All relevant experimental materials (datasets, questionnaires, surveys, training docs).
- *Experimental Infrastructure*: Any scripts, code, software, or experimental tools used in the study (including rationale, setup instructions, or version details).
- *Structure & Description*: The overall structure of the replication package (folders, naming conventions).
- *Data Analysis & Processing*: The study data as well as the methods and infrastructure used for data processing and analysis.
- * Rating: If there are inconsistencies, multiple ratings may be assigned to a single artifact.
 - *Mentioned*: The artifact is referenced in the publication without further details or description.
 - *Documented*: The artifact is described in detail within the publication.
 - *Accessible*: The artifact is available in an appendix, replication package, or any other publicly accessible source, allowing direct examination or reuse.
- * Decision: If multiple ratings were assigned to an artifact, the rating with the lowest value is considered for the decision process.
 - *Not Documented*: None of the research artifacts are documented or accessible.
 - *Partly Documented*: At least one of the essential research artifacts (*Experimental Design & Protocol*, *Experimental Materials*, *Experimental Infrastructure*, *Data Analysis & Processing*) is not documented or accessible.
 - *Documented*: All essential research artifacts (*Experimental Design & Protocol*, *Experimental Materials*, *Experimental Infrastructure*, *Data Analysis & Processing*) are documented or accessible.
 - *Fully Documented*: All research artifacts are documented and accessible in a public replication package.
- Participants: Essential information about participants including recruitment method, sample size, and basic demographics (age, gender). And additional bonus information about participants including power analysis and extended demographics (professional background, prior expertise).
 - * *No Participants Involved*: The paper does not include a human-oriented study.
 - * *Not Documented*: The paper does not mention any information about participants.
 - * *Partly Documented*: The paper reports some essential and/or bonus participant information, but at least one essential element is missing.
 - * *Documented*: The paper provides all essential participant information, but bonus information is incomplete or missing.
 - * *Fully Documented*: The paper mentions all essential and bonus information about participants.
- Metrics: Metrics used to evaluate the code recommender system, which can be assigned to at least one measurement objective (see Section 7.1 *D2*):
 - * *Not Documented*: The paper does not describe any metrics used.
 - * *Partly Documented*: At least one metric is mentioned and can be mapped to an attribute in the measurement objective list, but the description is incomplete.
 - * *Documented*: Two or more metrics are provided and mapped to attributes in the measurement objective list, but at least some lack key details such as definitions, formulas, scales, or scripts.
 - * *Fully Documented*: All described metrics can be mapped to attributes in the measurement objective list, with a complete explanation, including definitions, formulas, scales, and scripts.

V. 10

Out of the 481 candidate publications identified in the main search, 66 were marked as erroneous (see Table 11).

By reviewing the QGS publications that were not included in the main search, we identified one additional erroneous publications, bringing the total to 67.

For a detailed discussion, please refer to Section 9.

V. 10

To answer RQ1 and to present the documentation quality at the evaluation-method level, an additional quality assessment was conducted for publications reporting multiple evaluation methods ($n = 116$). Differences in documentation levels between evaluation methods within a single publication were recorded in the comment sections of each study setup detail in the publication-specific QA sheet and subsequently carried over to the “Overview” sheet.

6.4 Applications of Selection Criteria

The selection criteria are applied differently across the review phases: the establishment of the QGS corpus (see Section 4.2), the execution of the engine-based search (see Section 4.2), and the final backward-snowballing search (see Section 5).

6.4.1 Pilot-Study-specific Selection Process

We applied the selection criteria for the identification of suitable QGS publications when establishing the QGS corpus (see Section 4.2). However, for this purpose, the criteria and the procedure are slightly modified, primarily to maximize diversity across domains and publishers.

- Papers are initially screened based on their title, abstract, keywords, and section headings. If necessary, the introduction and conclusion sections are also reviewed. The application of the selection criteria is not performed in full, because of later changes in this process (C9 was revised after the QGS-specific selection process was completed).
- Due to the extensiveness of the manual screening step (see Section 6.3), quality assessment is not performed when deciding whether a publications is incorporated into the QGS corpus or not. However, QGS publications are assessed for quality at a later stage alongside the publications selected through the engine-specific selection process.

6.4.2 Engine-specific Selection Process

When applying the selection criteria during the engine-based search, the process differs from the QGS-specific phase in two important ways:

- AS with the QGS-specific process, papers are screened based on their title, abstract, keywords, section headings, and, if necessary, the introduction and conclusion sections.
- In this phase, quality assessment (see Section 6.3) is conducted immediately.

6.4.3 Procedure

Reviewers independently evaluate the publications in their assigned result set, ensuring mutual exclusion. Metadata-specific selection criteria are assessed within the search engine result sets, while content-specific selection criteria are applied after separating the publications into subsets. The detailed steps are listed below:

1. *Application of Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:* The reviewer applies predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria to determine the relevance of each publication (see Section 7.1). To maintain focus, reviewers are advised to take short breaks after every 30 minutes of work.
 - Metadata-specific Criteria Evaluation: Since metadata-specific criteria are objective, they are applied by the first author without secondary review.
 - Content-specific Criteria Evaluation: As content-specific criteria involve subjective assessment, these are verified by two independent reviewers:
 - C9: Publications are contextually evaluated in subsets, with each subset assigned to a single author. Only publications marked as Excluded(OT) C9 undergo a secondary review by the other author. Disagreements are resolved through a consensus discussion.
 - C10: Publications undergo a content-specific evaluation with a structured distribution process. Publications are randomly distributed while ensuring equal representation across search engines and publication timespans (Old [2017–2019], Middle [2020–2022], Recent [2023–2024]). Each publication is assigned to two different reviewers using round-robin assignment [57]. Initial rounds include group meetings to build a common understanding of the evaluation process. In later rounds, disagreements are resolved directly between reviewers with overlapping assignments.
2. *Quality Assessment:* For publications that meet the inclusion criteria, the first author evaluates compliance with the predefined quality criteria (see Section 6.3). Publications flagged as ERR undergo a secondary review by the second author. Disagreements are resolved via consensus discussion

6.5 Selection Validity

The selection procedure will result in ratings of multiple reviewers on different selection (C9, C10) and quality criteria. To quantify the level of agreement between these ratings (i.e., the inter-rater reliability; IRR), different agreement statistics are required to accommodate the respective rating procedures and underlying measurement scales [24]:

- *Percent Agreement* (p_a) [24] for reviewer confirmation procedures (C9 and Quality Assessment): For C9 and the Quality Assessment, each author assessed all publications from their subset, while the other author confirmed only items flagged as excluded. Since double ratings are available only for this subset, chance-corrected coefficients such as $\hat{\kappa}_c$ are not applicable. We will therefore report the p_a between the two authors on the confirmed cases, i.e., the proportion of decisions upheld by the secondary reviewer. This measure reflects the confirmation rate of primary reviewer decisions in these procedures.
- *Krippendorff’s Alpha* ($\hat{\alpha}_c$) [24] for pilot C10 ratings: In the pilot study, three independent reviewers rated one publication on a five-level ordinal relevance scale (“Not Relevant” to “Highly Relevant”). To quantify reliability among more than two reviewers on ordinal data, we will report $\hat{\alpha}_c$. This statistic accounts for the magnitude of disagreements between reviewers and supports varying numbers of reviewers, making it the most appropriate chance-corrected measure for this setup.
- *Cohen’s Weighted Kappa* ($\hat{\kappa}_c$) [24] for main C10 ratings: In the main study, the two authors independently rated all publications on the same five-level ordinal relevance scale. For this two-rater, ordinal-scale setup, we will report $\hat{\kappa}_c$ (quadratic weights). This coefficient corrects for chance agreement and penalizes larger disagreements more heavily, which aligns with the ordered nature of the rating scale.

V. 10

C9: In total, 1,862 publications were assessed against selection criterion C9 by the two authors:

- In the first round, 522 publications were excluded.
- In the second review, 456 of these exclusions were confirmed, corresponding to an agreement

proportion of $p_a = 82.75\%$.

- Among the 66 conflicts, 19 exclusions were upheld, while 47 publications were reclassified and reintegrated into the corpus for further review.

C10: In total, 1,387 publications were assessed against selection criterion C10 by two independent reviewers per publication. The review yielded the following weighted Cohen’s kappa coefficients ($\hat{\kappa}_c$) for the reviewer pairs:

- Daniel Borst - Kevin Innerebner: $\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.69$.
- Daniel Borst - Stefan Sobernig: $\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.72$.
- Daniel Borst - Leonie Greber: $\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.72$.
- Daniel Borst - Florian Poreba: $\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.67$.
- Overall: $\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.71$.
- These values indicate substantial agreement between reviewers [24].
- A more detailed overview of the analysis can be found in Table 5.

Quality Assessment: In total, 481 publications were assessed against the quality criterion by the first author. For publications included in the full review—i.e., those that received a “Highly Relevant” rating by at least one reviewer and remained included in case of disagreement—exclusions were cross-checked by the second author:

- In the first round, 78 publications were excluded, of which 18 (23.1%) had been marked for the full review.
- In the second review, 9 of these 18 exclusions were confirmed, corresponding to an agreement proportion of $p_a = 50.0\%$.
- Among the 9 conflicts, none of the exclusions were upheld, instead, all 9 publications were reclassified and reintegrated into the corpus for further review.

Table 5: Overview of the inter-rater reliability for selection criterion C10. The analysis distinguishes between the initial round, aimed at building a common understanding, and the subsequent rounds.

Pair	Initial Round	Total	Round 2	Round 3	Round 4	Round 5	Round 6	Round 7	Round 8	Total
Kevin Innerebner/ Florian Poreba	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.62$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.62$	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Kevin Innerebner/ Stefan Sobernig	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.30$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.30$	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Daniel Borst/ Florian Poreba	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.58$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.58$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.67$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.67$	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.67$
Stefan Sobernig/ Daniel Borst	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.47$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.47$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.74$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.70$	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.72$
Daniel Borst/ Kevin Innerebner	n/a	n/a	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.54$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.81$	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.69$
Daniel Borst/ Leonie Greber	n/a	n/a	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.64$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.87$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.67$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.61$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.63$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.81$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 1.0$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.72$
	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.44$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.44$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.65$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.76$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.67$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.61$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.63$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.81$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 1.0$	$\hat{\kappa}_c = 0.71$

7 Data Extraction

The data extraction procedure described below applies to the different phases of the review, including the establishment of the QGS corpus (see Section 4.2), the main engine-based search (see Section 4.2), and the final backward-snowballing search (see Section 5).

7.1 Data Records

- *Storage and Organization:* Data records are stored and managed as Excel spreadsheets, with each search engine having its own dedicated file named accordingly. The column structure in each sheet follows a standardized format as detailed below.
- *Independent Reviewers:* Two independent reviewers work on the same file but are blinded to each other's standardized sheets. This ensures unbiased data extraction while maintaining consistency across records.
- *Inter-Rater Reliability (IRR):* Although the goal is to achieve full agreement on each publication, IRR statistics are computed before negotiation to evaluate initial agreement levels and the complexity of reaching a consensus. We use Cohen's Kappa and Percent Agreement for inclusion/exclusion decisions and the Kupper-Hafner Index [58] for evaluating ratings of design-decision data.
- *Basic Data Record:* For each paper in the corpus, a basic data record is created. This data is extracted from both the content of the paper and the bibliographical metadata provided by the search engine. Depending on the data extraction capabilities of each search engine, some entries need to be generated through semi-automated processes or manual extraction (see Section 4.6).

The following data fields are to be extracted:

- *Data extractor 1:* Name of the first reviewer responsible for:
 - Conducting the authoritative search that identifies the publication as a search hit.
 - Making the initial selection decision based on the criteria outlined in Section 6.
 - Extracting the initial data record for the selected publication.
- *Data extractor 2:* Name of the second reviewer (must be different from the first extractor to ensure independent validation) responsible for:
 - A secondary selection decision using the same criteria (Section 6).
 - Extraction of a secondary data record.
- *Identifier:* A unique identifier is generated for each search engine result set to uniquely identify each publication within the search engine result set.
- *DOI:* The Document Object Identifier (DOI), as provided by the search engine.
- *Authors:* The list of authors, as retrieved from the search engine.
- *Title:* The publication title, as provided by the search engine.
- *Publication Year:* The year of publication, as listed by the search engine.
- *Page Range:* The range of pages, from the start to the final page, as retrieved from the search engine.
- *URL:* The URL associated with the publication. If available, DOI-resolver URLs are preferred over engine-specific or publisher-specific links.
- *Publisher:* The entity responsible for publishing the work (e.g., journal or proceedings publisher).
- *Keywords:* Keywords provided by the authors, if available.
- *Venue:* The publication venue of the article. Often synonymous with the title of the containing publication, if applicable (e.g., a proceedings or journal title).
- *Abstract:* The English abstract of the publication, if available.
- *Accessible:* A boolean operator indicating the full-text accessibility of the publication.

- *Access URL*: The URL to the publication’s full-text, if available.
- *Comments*: This field allows the extractors to leave notes or remarks. For excluded papers, this field also records the reason for exclusion (e.g., Included, Excluded (NMMC), Excluded (OT); see Sections 6.2 and 6.3).

V. 3

With the exception of the fields for data extractor 1, data extractor 2, and search engine, all other fields could be automatically extracted from the search engine results. Despite differences in labeling across various search engines, all necessary data fields were available and could be standardized with minimal effort. Occasionally, missing DOIs were encountered; when these were not automatically provided by the search engines, they were added either automatically (when possible) or manually for included papers.

V. 8

As part of the changes made to the selection criteria process (see Section 6.1), two new data fields, *Accessible* and *Access URL*, were introduced. The *Accessible* field indicates whether the full text of a publication is available through legal means, while the *Access URL* field provides the corresponding link to the source when accessible. These additions were necessary to document and track the outcomes of the automated accessibility checks performed using the Open Access Button and Unpaywall APIs.

For the papers identified through the engine-based search, two additional fields were captured:

- *Search Engine*: The name of the search engine that yielded the publication as a search hit.
- *Search Datetime*: A timestamp indicating when the search was conducted, leading to the identification of the publication.

For the papers included into the review result set (as per Section 6), we extract further design-specific data:

- *D1: Employed Evaluation Method*: This field documents the evaluation method used in the paper, as determined by the reviewers. One or more options are to be selected from the list if multiple evaluation methods were employed. However, each evaluation method should only be listed once. The following evaluation methods, as defined by Gunawardana and Shan [59] and adapted from Zangerle and Bauer [14], are considered:
 - Offline experiment: Evaluation using a simulation of user behavior based on past interactions, without human subjects and purely simulated tasks.
 - Human-involved offline experiment: Evaluation using datasets or benchmarks that involve human input, either for generating the dataset (human - code recommender system interaction) or judging the results, without live user interaction during the experiment.
 - Online evaluation: Evaluation using field experiments where users carry out their self-selected tasks in a real-world setting.
 - User study: Evaluations (in live or laboratory settings) with a set of human participants that carry out tasks as defined by the researcher.

V. 9

The Human-involved offline experiment evaluation method was additionally integrated to allow for a more detailed analysis. In contrast to other approaches adapted from Zangerle and Bauer [14], this method is newly introduced within the field, derived from the research strategies of Stol

and Fitzgerald [60].

V. 10

During data extraction, we encountered one study for which none of the predefined evaluation methods could be applied (explorative case study). We therefore introduced the category "Other" for D1 as well.

- *D2: Evaluation Metrics:* This field records the evaluation metrics and their corresponding measure used to evaluate code recommender systems, as identified by the reviewers. Metrics are understood as higher-level, somewhat subjective attributes often based on quantifiable, observable, and objective data [20]. The following information on metrics are to be extracted:
 - Metric Name, as stated in the publication.
 - D2.1: Metric Source. The following sources are considered:
 - * Defined by Authors: The metric was created or specifically adapted for the study by the authors
 - * From Other Publication: The metric was derived from a previous study or publication.
 - * Standard or Industry Benchmark: The metric comes from a recognized standard or industry benchmark, such as ISO, IEEE, or other relevant frameworks used widely in the field.
 - * Not Indicated: The source of the metric cannot be identified.
 - * Other: Any metric source not covered by the predefined categories.
 - D2.2: Measurement Objective. The following objectives inspired by Wang and Chen [16], based on the ISO/IEC 25010 [61] and ISO/IEC 25019 [62] standards (international guidelines for the evaluation of system and software quality), are considered:
 - * Acceptability: extent to which a human response is favorable when accepting or installing a system designed to perform some frequently used function.
 - * Functional Suitability: capability of a system to provide functions that meet stated and implied needs of intended users when it is used under specified conditions.
 - * Performance Efficiency: capability of a product to perform its functions within specified time and throughput parameters and be efficient in the use of resources under specified conditions.
 - * Reliability: capability of a system to perform specified functions under specified conditions for a specified period of time without interruptions and failures.
 - * Safety & Security: capability of a system under defined conditions to avoid endangering human life, health, property, or the environment, and to protect information and data by ensuring appropriate access levels based on authorization and defending against malicious attacks.
 - * Usability: extent to which a system can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a specified context of use.
 - * Other: Any measurement objective not captured by the standard categories listed above.
 - D2.3: Measurement Object. The following objects of measure are considered:
 - * Recommendation: Focuses on the artifacts (outputs) of the system in terms of the recommendations made to the developer.
 - * Developer: Targets the impact on the end-user while using the recommender system.
 - * System: Focuses on technical performance metrics of the system itself.
 - * Work Process: Focuses on the integration of the recommender system into the overall software development process.
 - * Other: Any measurement object not covered by the predefined categories.

In addition to the predefined measurement objectives, we conducted a further analysis of the three most prevalent ones, Functional Suitability, Usability, and Maintainability. Following the ISO/IEC 25010 [61] and ISO/IEC 25019 [62] standards, we classified reported metrics according to the relevant sub-characteristics of each quality attribute:

- Functional Suitability:
 - * Functional completeness: capability of a product to provide a set of functions that covers all specified tasks and objectives.
 - * Functional correctness: capability of a product to provide accurate and precise results.
 - * Functional appropriateness: capability of a product to provide functions that facilitate the accomplishment of specified tasks and objectives.
 - * Other: Any Functional Suitability sub-characteristic not captured by the standard categories listed above.
- Usability:
 - * Learnability: capability of a product to allow specified users to learn to use functions within a specified amount of time.
 - * Operability: capability of a product to provide functions and attributes that make it easy to operate and control.
 - * Effectiveness: accuracy and completeness with which users achieve specified goals.
 - * Efficiency: resources expended in relation to the accuracy and completeness with which users achieve goals.
 - * Satisfaction: freedom from discomfort and positive attitudes towards the use of the product.
 - * Other: Any Usability sub-characteristic not captured by the standard categories listed above.
- Maintainability:
 - * Modifiability: capability of a product to be effectively and efficiently modified without introducing defects or degrading existing quality.
 - * Analyzability: capability of a product to be effectively and efficiently assessed to diagnose deficiencies, failures, or necessary changes.
 - * Other: Any Maintainability sub-characteristic not captured by the standard categories listed above.

We decided to not include this further analysis into the paper and plan to investigate this further in upcoming studies.

- *D3: Software Engineering Area:* This field identifies the software engineering area(s) addressed by the paper, as determined by the reviewers. One or more options are to be selected from the list if multiple software engineering areas are addressed. However, each software engineering area should only be listed once. The following six software engineering areas, derived from SWEBOK [63] and adapted from Del Carpio and Angarita [19], are considered:
 - Software Requirements: The process of eliciting, analyzing, specifying, validating, and managing requirements from stakeholders, resulting in requirements specification documents.
 - Software Design: The process of creating various design models that translate requirements into software architecture, components, and interfaces, utilizing modeling, prototyping, and analysis techniques.
 - Software Construction: The process covering the activities involved in translating the software design into executable code.

- Software Testing: The process of systematically exercising the software to validate behavior, detect defects, and verify quality conformance through test planning, execution, analysis, and defect tracking.
- Software Maintenance: The process of managing modifications, enhancements, and corrections throughout the software’s lifecycle, including bug fixes, updates, performance improvements, and retirement.
- Software Configuration Management: The process of tracking and controlling changes to a software system. It includes version control, identifying configuration items, controlling changes, auditing for compliance, and tracking the status of configuration items and their relationships, along with the establishment of baselines.
- Other: Any software engineering area not covered by the predefined categories above.

V. 4

We decided not to include the following SWEBOK [63] software engineering areas: Software Engineering Management, Software Engineering Process, Software Engineering Tools and Methods, Software Engineering Quality. While these domains are integral to broader software engineering practices, they are considered too high-level for the purposes of this review. These areas primarily focus on processes, administration, and overall project governance rather than the core development activities relevant to code recommender systems. Instead, this review will concentrate on more directly related aspects, where the practical application and evaluation of recommender systems can be more effectively analyzed.

- *D4: Code Recommender System Operation:* This field identifies the specific operation provided by the recommender system, as determined by the reviewers. One or more options are to be selected from the list if multiple code recommender system operations are addressed. However, each code recommender system operation should only be listed once. The following code recommender system operations, defined by Almonte [1], are considered:
 - Complete: Extending an existing artifact by providing suggestions for enhancement.
 - Create: Constructing an initial version of a new artifact from scratch.
 - Find: Assisting in the discovery of relevant elements or artifacts within a repository.
 - Repair: Offering solutions to fix errors in an existing artifact, which may involve creating, deleting, or modifying elements within the artifact.
 - Reuse: Facilitating the reuse of an existing artifact (or part of it) within another context, with guidance on how to integrate the reused artifact effectively.
 - Other: Any code recommender system operation not covered by the predefined categories above.
- *D5: Software Language:* This field categorizes the type of software language supported by the recommender system, as identified by the reviewers. One or more options are to be selected from the list if multiple software languages are addressed. However, each software language should only be listed once. The following gradual classification scheme is used:
 1. Language Type:
 - Modeling Languages: Software languages used to represent systems or processes, often used to visually or textually describe the behavior, structure, or functionality, and not necessarily resulting in executable programs
 - Programming Languages: Software languages used to write executable code that runs on a computer.
 2. Application Scope:
 - Domain-Specific Languages (DSL): Software languages tailored to a specific domain or area of interest, offering specialized syntax and semantics for tasks within that domain.

- Domain-Independent (General Purpose) Languages: Software languages that are not restricted to a specific application area and can be used to develop a wide range of software, applications, and systems.

3. Notation:

- Graphical Notation: Involves visual elements like diagrams, symbols, or blocks.
- Textual Notation: Involves writing code or commands in a text-based format, including symbols such as integrals or fraction bars.
- Tabular Notation: Uses tables or structured grids to represent data or system rules.

V. 4

While initially considered, Recommendation Enactment: manual, interactive, automated, semi-automated, and Recommendation Trigger: on-demand, proactively, both, were ultimately excluded from the design-specific data extraction. These aspects relate to the technical specifications and interaction models of the code recommender systems, but they do not significantly influence the evaluation process. The focus of the evaluation is on productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, and perceived satisfaction with code recommender systems, rather than the specific mechanisms by which recommendations are delivered or triggered. Thus, they were considered less relevant for this review.

- *D6: Reported Threats:* This field identifies the study design limitations explicitly described by the authors as potential threats to the validity of their findings. Only limitations recognized by the authors themselves are considered, excluding aspects they do not regard as threats. This approach is based on the procedure described by Wyrich [64], with slight adaptations. Unlike the original procedure, it also includes threats that the authors report as mitigated, as their acknowledgment indicates relevance to the study’s validity. Wyrich et al.’s work also includes subcategories for threat areas to provide a more detailed analysis. However, we did not include these subcategories in our SLR because they are explicitly tailored to controlled experiments within the domain of code comprehension. Since reported threats are not the main focus of our SLR, and our review encompasses a broader range of study designs beyond controlled experiments, we believe that the overarching threat area categories allows us to capture the essential information.
 - D6.1: Types of Validity Threats. One or more options are to be selected from the list if multiple validity threat types are addressed. However, each validity threat type should only be listed once. If the authors employed the same classification scheme, their categorization is to be adopted as reported. The following types, as defined by Jedlitschka et al. [65], are considered:
 - * Internal: Refers to whether the independent variable(s) truly caused the observed effects on the dependent variable, without interference from confounding factors.
 - * External: Refers to how well the study’s findings can be generalized to other populations, settings, or contexts.
 - * Construct: Refers to the accuracy of the measurement methods in representing the theoretical concepts being studied.
 - * Conclusion: Refers to whether the conclusions drawn from the data are correct and supported by appropriate analysis.
 - * Other: Includes additional validity threat types, such as ethical concerns, conflicts of interest, or personal biases that may affect the study.
 - D6.2: Threat Areas. One or more options are to be selected from the list if multiple threat areas are addressed. However, each threat area should only be listed once. The following areas, as defined by Siegmund and Schumann [66], are considered:
 - * Participants: Concerns related to the selection and characteristics of participants, including biases or unrepresentative samples.
 - * Materials: Issues with the suitability of tools, software, or datasets used in the study.

- * Task Design: Problems with how tasks were structured, potentially making results less applicable to real-world scenarios.
- * Operationalization and measurement: Issues with how variables were defined and measured, affecting the accuracy of the findings.
- * Research design, procedure and conduct: Concerns about the overall design and execution of the study, including biases or inconsistencies in procedure.
- * Data analysis: Problems related to data analysis methods, including the use of incorrect statistical techniques or biased interpretation.
- * Other: Includes additional threat areas not covered by the predefined areas above.

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We decided to adapt the data extraction process for analytical purposes. Instead of extracting every data entry individually and recording each category type only once per entry, we extracted data records D1–D5 separately for every identified metric to enable subsequent cross-tabulation. Additionally, for D6, each reported validity threat was extracted with its corresponding type and area for every evaluation method. If threats of the same type and area appeared multiple times within and across evaluation methods for a publications, this was explicitly noted and their frequency was documented.

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In the deduplication process, we identified that ACM226 and Sco1021 referred to the same publication, despite differences in title wording and DOI metadata. To avoid double counting, we retained the ACM entry and removed Sco1021 from the dataset.

For D5, seven publications [46], [47], [67]–[71] did not report any identifiable software language. For D6, 13 publications [32], [68], [69], [72]–[81] did not provide any explicitly stated design limitations by the authors, so this information could not be extracted. In all these cases, the respective fields were marked as not reported.

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Insights gained throughout the data extraction procedure and the discussion rounds for comparing the independent ratings between the two authors:

- D2: Any metric that contains subcategories, such as a questionnaire or aggregated score, needs to be fully extracted (if accessible). This means that every subcategory (e.g., each question of a SUS score) is to be extracted as an individual metric. Additionally, the overall score should also be extracted if applicable (e.g., ACM41 [82], ACM52 [83], IEEE94 [84]).
- D2: Evaluations based on free text, think-aloud protocols, interviews, or similar qualitative methods are only to be extracted if the data were processed into quantifiable metrics (e.g., SCO345 [85], IEEE74 [69], ACM20 [86]).
- D2.1: For clarity, the Metric Source category *Standard or Industry Benchmark* was renamed to *Standards*.
- D2.1: The Metric Source category *Defined by Authors* is to be selected if a definition of the metric is provided in the text. *Not Indicated* should only be selected if no definition is provided. Metrics are to be labeled as *From Other Publication* or *Standard* only if the authors explicitly provide a corresponding reference.
- D2.1: Three additional Metric Source categories emerged through inductive coding, based on 43 instances initially classified as *Other*:

- Software Tooling: The metric is derived from software tools, such as static analyzers or bug-fixing tools (e.g., SCO45 [42], IEEE264 [87]).
- Online Coding Platform: The metric is automatically measured on an online coding platform during task execution (e.g., SCO366 [80], SCO1126 [88]).
- Website: The metric originates from a website (e.g., ACM177 [89]).
- D2.2: The definitions of the Measurement Objectives were adapted to make them more general, as the ISO/IEC definitions [61], [62] are typically specified for a particular measurement object.
 - Acceptability: Extent to which a measurement object is perceived as appropriate, useful, or favorable by its intended users or stakeholders.
 - Functional Suitability: Degree to which a measurement object provides functions or outcomes that meet stated or implied requirements of its intended purpose.
 - Performance Efficiency: Degree to which a measurement object achieves its intended outcomes using time, computational, or human resources effectively.
 - Reliability: Degree to which a measurement object consistently produces expected results under comparable conditions without errors or breakdowns.
 - Safety & Security: Extent to which a measurement object prevents harm, safeguards assets, and ensures appropriate protection of information and access.
 - Usability: Degree to which a measurement object can be understood, learned, and effectively used by its intended users to achieve desired goals with efficiency and satisfaction.
 - Other: Any measurement objective not adequately represented by the categories listed above.
- D2.2: Four new Measurement Objective categories were identified through inductive coding, based on 96 instances initially classified as *Other*:
 - Maintainability: Extent to which a measurement object can be modified by the intended maintainers with effectiveness and efficiency [61] (e.g., ACM47 [90], SCO1126 [88]).
 - Cognitive Capabilities: The mental workload imposed on a developer while performing a development task (e.g., ACM52 [83], IEEE37 [91]).
 - System Interaction: The behavioral characteristics of interactions between a developer and the system during a development task (e.g., ACM20 [86], ACM52 [83]).
 - Reasoning: The reasoning capabilities of a developer during a development task (e.g., SCO691 [92]).
- D2.3: The Measurement Object refers to the entity that was directly evaluated. For example, if study participants are asked about the correctness of recommendations provided by the CRS, the Measurement Object is classified as *Developer* rather than *Recommendation*.
 - This approach also allows the combination of the Measurement Object *Developer* with developer-unspecific Measurement Objectives, such as *Functional Suitability* or *Maintainability*.
- D2.3: One additional Measurement Object category was identified through inductive coding of 39 instances initially labeled as *Other*:
 - Code Artifact: Focuses on recommendations that are adapted by a developer and subsequently evaluated (e.g., ACM2 [93]).
- D3: Activities involving the creation of code-level documentation (e.g., generating code comments and code summaries) are classified under the SE Area *Software Construction*, in line with the SWEBOK definitions [63], rather than under *Software Maintenance*.

- D3: Multiple SE Area options should only be extracted for a publication if the evaluation includes multiple distinct tasks. For each individual task, exactly one SE Area must be assigned, reflecting the primary SE Area addressed by that task. For example, if participants are asked to create a code artifact from scratch and, in the process, identify and resolve errors in their code, only the SE Area *Software Construction* should be selected. Although error identification and resolution may occur, these activities do not represent the primary goal of the task and therefore do not constitute a separate assignment to the SE Area *Software Testing*.
- D4: Four new Code Recommender System Operation categories were identified through inductive coding, based on 15 instances initially classified as *Other*:
 - Analyze: Analyzing an existing artifact to provide feedback (e.g., IEEE74 [69], ACM25 [94]).
 - Diagnose: Identifying errors in an existing code artifact (e.g., ACM199 [72], ACM88 [95]).
 - Modify: Modifying an existing code artifact to improve properties such as code quality or maintainability (e.g., IEEE67 [46], SCO81 [96]).
 - Translate: Translating an existing code artifact into another software language (e.g., IEEE107 [97]).
- D6.1: Two additional Types of Validity Threats emerged through inductive coding, based on eight instances initially classified as *Other*:
 - Reliability: Refers to whether data collection, analysis, and storage are conducted in a way that enables transparent and traceable research (e.g., SCO1126 [88], SCO462 [98]).
 - Replicability: Refers to whether the study can be replicated by independent researchers (e.g., IEEE568 [99], ACM63 [100]).

Table 6: Alignment of key metadata fields across the result sets retrieved by the four search engines. "n/a" indicates fields not available in a given result set.

	ACMDL	IEEEXplore	Scopus	SpringerLink
doi	doi	DOI	DOI	DOI
author	author	Authors	Authors	Authors
title	title	Document Title	Title	Title
publication year	year	Publication Year	Year	Publication Year
page range	numpages	Start Page, End Page	Page count	n/a
url	url	PDF Link	Link	URL
venue	booktitle, journal	Publication Title	Source title	Venue
publisher	publisher	Publisher	Publisher	Publisher
abstract	abstract	Abstract	Abstract	Abstract
keywords	keywords	Author Keywords	Author Keywords	n/a

Table 7: Overview of search engine result set overlaps based on identical DOIs identified in the automated detection. Each cell in the lower triangle displays the absolute count of identical DOIs between two result sets. The upper triangle cells present the overlap ratios of non-unique DOIs between the two result sets, in relation to their total publication counts. Diagonal cells indicate the total number of publications with non-unique DOIs within each result set.

	ACMDL	IEEEXplore	Scopus	SpringerLink
ACMDL	284	5.7%	9.3%	0%
IEEEXplore	63	632	18%	0%
Scopus	282	630	965	3.8%
SpringerLink	0	0	114	114

Table 8: Overview of search engine result set overlaps based on identical titles identified in the automated detection. Each cell in the lower triangle displays the absolute count of identical titles between two result sets. The upper triangle cells present the overlap ratios of non-unique titles between the two result sets, in relation to their total publication counts. Diagonal cells indicate the total number of publications with non-unique titles within each result set.

	ACMDL	IEEEXplore	Scopus	SpringerLink
ACMDL	1	0%	0.03%	n/a
IEEEXplore	0	1	0.03%	n/a
Scopus	1	1	2	n/a
SpringerLink	0	0	0	0

Table 9: Results of the automated duplicate-marking steps, distinguishing between intra-source duplicates (within a single engine’s result set) and inter-source duplicates (across result sets from the four engines).

	ACMDL	IEEEXplore	Scopus	SpringerLink	Σ
# search hits	347	752	2,694	308	4,101
# duplicated hits	0	63	979	0	1,042
# cleaned hits	347	689	1,715	308	3,059
before DOI cleansing					
# hits without DOI	4	52	285	0	341
# hits with DOI	343	700	2,409	308	3,760
intra-source duplicates					
# based on DOI	0	0	10	0	10
# based on title matching	0	0	2	0	2
inter-source duplicates					
# based on DOI	284	632	965	114	n/a
# based on title match	1	1	2	0	n/a

Table 10: Overview of per-engine quasi-sensitivity for the four search engines and their respective result sets.

	expected	intra-source	inter-source
ACMDL	11	5	5
IEEEXplore	6	7	10
Scopus	5	11	23
SpringerLink	3	1	1

Table 11: Overview of excluded/included publications during selection (NMMC, OT) and quality assessment (ERR).

Hits/publications	ACMDL	IEEEExplore	Scopus	SpringerLink	Main Search	QGS	Total
Total	347	752	2,694	308	4,101	25	4,126
Unique	346	658	1,691	308	3,003	1	3,004
Excluded (NMMC)	115	360	583	88	1,146	0	1,146
Excluded (OT)	143	199	854	181	1,377	0	1,377
ERR	8	13	33	12	66	1	67
Extensions merged	2	2	5	0	9	0	9
Included	79	85	214	27	405	0	405
Included first round	33	26	29	4	92	0	92

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For the paper, the reporting of data differs slightly from the protocol: extensions identified during the quality assessment were merged with their original publications. These merged cases are reported under the category Excluded (NMMC) in the paper, which may cause minor deviations in the reported numbers.

Figure 4: Distribution of the types of artifacts investigated in the set of publications assessed against selection criterion C9. The figure shows how frequently different artifact types were addressed across the considered publications.

Figure 5: Distribution of the most common reasons for exclusion among the publications assessed against selection criterion C9. The figure illustrates how frequently different exclusion reasons were applied during the assessment process.

7.2 Procedure

Full data extraction is conducted by the first author for all publications. To ensure validity in the extraction of design-decision data, the second author independently conducts data extraction on a sample of the publications. The detailed steps are listed below:

1. *Verification of Automatically Extracted Data:* The first author reviews and verifies the automatically extracted data records for each publication (see Section 7.1). Since the verification of automatically extracted metadata can be assessed objectively, it is performed by a single reviewer without secondary review.
2. *Design-Decision Data Extraction:* For publications that meet the inclusion criteria and pass the quality assessment, the authors independently proceed to extract the design-decision data from the included publications (see Section 7.1):
 - Data entries (D1-D6) from all publications are extracted by the first author.
 - Data entries (D1-D6) from a sample of the publications are extracted independently by the second author. The sample size is determined based on the deviation observed in the relevance ranking of publications for selection criterion C10 (see Section 6.1). Only publications included for the full review are considered, i.e., those that received a “Highly Relevant” rating by at least one reviewer and remained included in case of disagreement. Among these, all publications rated below “Relevant” by the second reviewer are considered to show a strong deviation, since “Relevant” represents the threshold for inclusion. Out of the 92 publications with at least one “Highly Relevant” rating, 13 showed a strong deviation, corresponding to approximately 15%. Assuming a similar deviation rate in the remaining 79 publications, this would amount to an additional 12 publications (79×0.15). Together with the 13 publications already identified, this results in a total of 25 publications, equivalent to 27% of the total volume. The 12 additional publications are selected using stratified simple random sampling without replacement [101]. Three strata are defined (“QGS”, “Highly Relevant/Relevant”, “Highly Relevant/Highly Relevant”), each repre-

senting a distinct subset of the publication pool. From each stratum, four unique publications are randomly drawn.

- Disagreements are resolved via consensus discussions.

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To optimize workflow efficiency, the design-specific data *D1: Employed Evaluation Method* was extracted during the quality assessment procedure. This strategy allowed for preliminary data organization before full extraction.

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We were able to extract design-specific data for all publications included in the final corpus. For RQ1, data was extracted from the 477 publications subjected to quality assessment.

- For data record D1, we extracted a total of 589 entries corresponding to evaluation methods.
- A single evaluation method was extracted for 362 publications, while 115 publications contained two evaluation methods combined within the same study.
- With the exception of one publication, all extracted evaluation methods could be assigned to the predefined categories.

For RQ2–RQ4, design-specific data was extracted in a first round (see Section 6.1) from 92 publications with a major focus on the evaluation of code recommender systems.

- For data record D2, we extracted 579 entries corresponding to metrics. For all entries, sufficient details were available to assign a corresponding measurement objective and object.
- For data record D3, we extracted 125 entries corresponding to software engineering areas. All evaluation methods could be assigned except one, where insufficient information was provided.
- For data record D4, we extracted 130 entries corresponding to code recommender operations. An operation was identified for all but one evaluation method, where insufficient details were available.
- For data record D5, we extracted 104 entries corresponding to software languages. For seven evaluation methods, the exact software language was not reported and could therefore not be extracted.
- For data record D6, we extracted 361 threats to validity entries from 79 of the 92 publications.

7.3 Reliability

The extraction procedure will produce independent ratings from two reviewers (see Section 7.2) on the design-specific data fields (D1–D6). Inter-rater reliability (IRR) is quantified using a single statistic that is well-suited to the characteristics of the extracted data:

- *Kupper-Hafner (KH) [58] Index*: This index is applied to assess agreement between the two authors across the design-specific data fields (D1–D6). Each extractor may assign one or more decision options per field, resulting in multi-label nominal data. The available options for each field correspond to the decision categories defined in Section 7.1. The Kupper–Hafner (KH) index will be reported as the primary reliability statistic, as it captures agreement on both included and excluded options and is robust in the presence of prevalence imbalances that are common in multi-label coding schemes [58].

In total, data from 27 publications were extracted by the two authors independently, comprising 4,697 individual decision options. Across all decisions, an inter-rater reliability (IRR) of $KH = 0.62$ was achieved. Data extraction categories D1, D3, D4, and D5 showed high reliability (0.93–0.99), whereas categories D2 and D6 reached comparatively lower scores of 0.47 and 0.74, respectively. The lower reliability of D2 and D6 can be attributed to their increased complexity, as both required the identification of items (i.e., metrics or threats to validity) and involved multiple subcategories, thereby increasing the number of decision options. For D2, a total of 165 items were identified, of which 114 were recognized by both extractors. For D6, 84 items were identified, with 73 recognized by both extractors. While the categorization of D6 was based on predefined schemes established in prior secondary studies [64], the scheme for D2 was newly developed by us. Consequently, several decision options allowed for interpretative variation, leading to differing understandings of certain categories and, ultimately, a lower IRR. This also resulted in frequent use of the residual "Other" category, which further contributed to disagreement between extractors. These discrepancies were subsequently discussed, a shared understanding was reached, and the resulting adjustments were systematically applied to all subsequent decisions. The most important insights from the discussion are documented in Section 7.1.

Table 12: Overview of inter-rater reliability in data extraction, measured using the Kupper–Hafner Index (KH). Values are reported per top-level data extraction category (D1–D6) and for the overall weighted agreement across all decisions.

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	Total
KH	0.99	0.47	0.95	0.93	0.98	0.74	0.62

8 Data Analysis

The data analysis section outlines the steps taken to answer each of the three research questions. The analysis will involve quantifying the prevalence of different evaluation methods, exploring how these methods are applied across various contexts, and investigating the metrics and measures used to assess the impact of code recommender systems. For each research question, a systematic approach will be followed to analyze and interpret the extracted data (see Section 7) from the identified studies. The goal is to uncover patterns, relationships, and trends that provide insights into the evaluation of code recommender systems in software development. By identifying gaps and trends in evaluation practices, this analysis will highlight areas where future research is needed. Ultimately, the results of this study will form the basis for the development of a comprehensive framework for the evaluation of code recommender systems.

- *RQ1: Prevalence of evaluation methods:* To answer RQ1, we will analyze the distribution of different evaluation methods (offline, online, and user studies) used across the identified literature. This will help determine which methods are most frequently employed to assess code recommender systems.
 - Prevalence of evaluation methods: Compute the frequency of each evaluation method across all identified studies.
 - Documentation Quality: Calculate the prevalence of documentation level across artifacts, participants, and metrics.
 - Identify Replicability: Analyze how many of the studies are replicable using the data from the quality assessment (see Section 6.3). Only studies ranked "Documented" in the fields of metrics and participants (if applicable) and "Fully Documented" in the field of artifacts are considered reproducible.
 - Cross-Tabulation of Evaluation Methods and Reproducibility: Investigate the prevalence of reproducible studies across different evaluation methods.

- *RQ2: Use of evaluation method:* To address RQ2, we will explore how different evaluation methods are applied within various software engineering areas, recommender system operations, and software languages. This cross-tabulation analysis will highlight patterns in how evaluation methods are used in different contexts.
 - Cross-Tabulation of Evaluation Methods and Software Engineering Areas: Analyze how each evaluation method is distributed across the different software engineering areas.
 - Cross-Tabulation of Evaluation Methods and Recommender System Operations: Investigate how evaluation methods correspond to the recommender system operations.
 - Cross-Tabulation of Evaluation Methods and Software Languages: Investigate how evaluation methods vary with the types of software languages used.
 - Cross-Tabulation of Multiple Factors: Perform cross-tabulations combining software engineering areas, recommender system operations, and software languages to identify any multi-variable patterns in how evaluation methods are applied.
- *RQ3: Metrics:* For RQ3, the goal is to understand the evaluation metrics employed to evaluate the impact of code recommender systems. This involves classifying metrics, analyzing their prevalence, and examining in what context they were used across studies.
 - Categorize Evaluation Metrics: Classify the evaluation metrics used in each study.
 - Calculate Prevalence of Metrics: Quantify the prevalence of each metric across studies to identify the most commonly used metrics.
 - Analyze Metric Combinations: Investigate how metrics are combined within studies, and identify frequently recurring combinations used to assess code recommender systems.
 - Compare Measures Across Metrics: Explore whether the same evaluation metrics are measured differently across studies, analyzing variability in the applied measures.

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As stated in Section 7.1, all metrics containing subcategories were fully extracted. To avoid skewing the results, since some subcategories corresponded to extensive lists of additional metrics (e.g., a productivity score consisting of 12 questions, see ACM226 [102]), we decided to group such metrics under specific conditions. Metrics were grouped only if they referred to the same measurement objective and measurement object, and if the publication reported them as an aggregated metric across all subcategories. (e.g., SPR105 [71], ACM226 [102], SCO275 [79]).

- *RQ4: Reported threats to validity:* To answer RQ4, we will analyze the threats to validity and limitations that are reported by the authors in the identified studies. This will provide insight into the common validity concerns associated with studies evaluating code recommender systems and help identify which areas of study design are most frequently affected.
 - Prevalence of Threats to Validity Types: Compute the frequency of each threats to validity type across the studies
 - Prevalence of Threats to Validity Areas: Compute the frequency of each threats to validity area across the studies
 - Cross-Tabulation of Threats to Validity Types with Evaluation Methods: Investigate how threats to validity types are distributed across different evaluation methods
 - Cross-Tabulation of Threats to Validity Areas with Evaluation Methods: Investigate how threats to validity areas are distributed across different evaluation methods

9 Documentation Quality of Code Recommender System Evaluations

Our SLR revealed notable shortcomings in a substantial number of studies evaluating code recommender systems. These shortcomings stem primarily from limited or missing reporting of essential aspects of the study setup, including research artifacts, study participants, and employed metrics. While such omissions may be less critical if the sole aim was to communicate results, they reduce the reliability of the findings and hinder the repeatability of the studies. Although only very few publications achieved comprehensive documentation quality, we excluded only those with severe reporting defects in at least one study setup detail, as such deficiencies undermine reliability and often obscure information required in the data extraction step.

In total, 67 publications were excluded during quality assessment because their documentation of the study setup was erroneous (see Section 6.3). Below we summarize the most critical defects observed. Importantly, we also report defects that did not always result in exclusion, yet we consider it valuable to highlight them so they can be avoided in future research.

Missing External Sources: Only 67.5% (324/480) of the publications analyzed in the quality assessment provided access to external artifacts. Providing study materials through a replication package is essential for ensuring transparency and repeatability. Such packages allow other researchers to re-run studies under the same conditions, verify reported findings, and reduce ambiguity regarding the use of materials, datasets, and scripts. External availability of study artifacts therefore strengthens credibility and ensures that results can at least be repeated, even if full replication in different contexts is not intended.

Missing Dataset Information: Finally, many studies failed to provide sufficient information about the datasets used. Missing details such as dataset origin, size, preprocessing steps, or representativeness severely limit the credibility and interpretability of results. Inadequate dataset reporting makes it impossible to evaluate whether the dataset was appropriate for the research questions or to enable comparison across studies. Moreover, it hinders repeatability, as other researchers cannot reproduce the analysis conditions. Transparent dataset reporting is therefore fundamental to evaluating study validity and ensuring that conclusions are grounded in clearly defined data.

Missing Power Analysis: A recurring defect in human-centered studies was the absence of a power analysis. A power analysis is a statistical procedure used to determine the minimum sample size required to detect an effect of a given size with a specified level of confidence and probability of detection. Conducting a power analysis is crucial in human-centered research to ensure that sample sizes are sufficient to detect meaningful effects, thereby reducing the risk of false negatives, avoiding unnecessary use of participant resources, and increasing the overall validity of the study design [103].

Missing Demographic Information: Another common defect was the lack of reported demographic information about study participants. Demographic details are vital for interpreting results and assessing their generalizability. Factors such as age, gender, expertise, or educational background can significantly influence how participants interact with a system or task. Without this context, it is difficult to determine whether findings apply to broader populations or are limited to a specific group. Transparent reporting of demographic data thus enhances validity, supports cross-study comparisons, and allows more informed judgments about the applicability of results.

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Appendix A Overview Of Coverage Of Tasks Supported By Code Recommender Systems In Secondary Studies

Table 13: Coverage of tasks supported by CRSs as reported in four secondary studies [7], [9], [10], [104]. A checkmark indicates that a given study explicitly categorizes CRSs as supporting the corresponding task. Tasks that were referred to with different names in the original sources (e.g., “Bug Finding” and “Defect Detection”) were merged for consistency.

Task	Al-Hossami et al.	Wong et al.	Wan et al.	Savary-Leblanc et al.
API/Code Search	×	×	×	✓
Bug Finding/Defect Detection	✓	✓	✓	×
Clone Detection	✓	✓	✓	×
Cloze Testing	✓	×	×	×
Code Classification	×	×	✓	×
Code Completion	✓	✓	✓	✓
Code Documentation Generation	✓	×	×	×
Code Generation	✓	✓	×	×
Code Metrics	×	×	×	✓
Code Refinement	✓	✓	×	×
Code Search	✓	×	✓	×
Code Summarization	×	✓	✓	×
Code Translation/Program Translation	✓	✓	✓	×
Code Visualization	×	×	×	✓
Command Recommendation	×	×	×	✓
Documentation Translation	✓	×	×	×
Finding Collaborators	×	×	×	✓
Fix and Repair/Program Repair	✓	×	✓	✓
Interface Prototyping	×	×	×	✓
Modeling	×	×	×	✓
Program Analysis	✓	×	×	×
Program Synthesis	✓	×	✓	×
Refactoring	×	×	×	✓
Resource Identification	×	×	×	✓
Semantic Parsing	✓	×	×	×
Type Inference	×	×	✓	×
Version Control Systems	×	×	×	✓
Vulnerability Detection	×	×	✓	×

Appendix B Engine-specific Search Strings

Listing 5: ACMDL, submitted via the web UI (form).

Title:(("evaluat*" OR "assess*" OR "study" OR "experiment") AND ("github copilot" OR "ai pair programmer" OR "code assistant" OR "openai codex" OR "query recommendation" OR "code completion" OR "code intelligence" OR "code recommendation" OR "refactoring recommendation" OR "code generation" OR "import generation" OR "commit message generation" OR "code comment generation" OR "code documentation generation" OR "automatic program synthesis" OR "assert statement recommendation" OR "code summarization" OR "code summarisation" OR "language workbench" OR "bug fixing" OR "type recommendation" OR "modelling chatbot" OR "code synthesis")) OR Abstract:(("evaluat*" OR "assess*" OR "study" OR "experiment") AND ("github copilot" OR "ai pair programmer" OR "code assistant" OR "openai codex" OR "query recommendation" OR "code completion" OR "code intelligence" OR "code recommendation" OR "refactoring recommendation" OR "code generation" OR "import generation" OR "commit message generation" OR "code comment generation" OR "code documentation generation" OR "automatic

program synthesis" OR "assert statement recommendation" OR "code summarization" OR "code summarisation" OR "language workbench" OR "bug fixing" OR "type recommendation" OR "modelling chatbot" OR "code synthesis")) OR Keyword:(("evaluat*" OR "assess*" OR "study" OR "experiment") AND ("github copilot" OR "ai pair programmer" OR "code assistant" OR "openai codex" OR "query recommendation" OR "code completion" OR "code intelligence" OR "code recommendation" OR "refactoring recommendation" OR "code generation" OR "import generation" OR "commit message generation" OR "code comment generation" OR "code documentation generation" OR "automatic program synthesis" OR "assert statement recommendation" OR "code summarization" OR "code summarisation" OR "language workbench" OR "bug fixing" OR "type recommendation" OR "modelling chatbot" OR "code synthesis"))

Listing 6: IEEEExplore, submitted via the web UI (form).

```
(("Abstract": "evaluat*" OR "Abstract": "assess*" OR "Abstract": "study" OR "Abstract": "experiment") AND ("Abstract": "github copilot" OR "Abstract": "ai pair programmer" OR "Abstract": "code assistant" OR "Abstract": "openai codex" OR "Abstract": "query recommendation" OR "Abstract": "code completion" OR "Abstract": "code intelligence" OR "Abstract": "code recommendation" OR "Abstract": "refactoring recommendation" OR "Abstract": "code generation" OR "Abstract": "import generation" OR "Abstract": "commit message generation" OR "Abstract": "code comment generation" OR "Abstract": "code documentation generation" OR "Abstract": "automatic program synthesis" OR "Abstract": "assert statement recommendation" OR "Abstract": "code summarization" OR "Abstract": "code summarisation" OR "Abstract": "language workbench" OR "Abstract": "bug fixing" OR "Abstract": "type recommendation" OR "Abstract": "modelling chatbot" OR "Abstract": "code synthesis")) OR (("Document Title": "evaluat*" OR "Document Title": "assess*" OR "Document Title": "study" OR "Document Title": "experiment") AND ("Document Title": "github copilot" OR "Document Title": "ai pair programmer" OR "Document Title": "code assistant" OR "Document Title": "openai codex" OR "Document Title": "query recommendation" OR "Document Title": "code completion" OR "Document Title": "code intelligence" OR "Document Title": "code recommendation" OR "Document Title": "refactoring recommendation" OR "Document Title": "code generation" OR "Document Title": "import generation" OR "Document Title": "commit message generation" OR "Document Title": "code comment generation" OR "Document Title": "code documentation generation" OR "Document Title": "automatic program synthesis" OR "Document Title": "assert statement recommendation" OR "Document Title": "code summarization" OR "Document Title": "code summarisation" OR "Document Title": "language workbench" OR "Document Title": "bug fixing" OR "Document Title": "type recommendation" OR "Document Title": "modelling chatbot" OR "Document Title": "code synthesis")) OR (("Author Keywords": "evaluat*" OR "Author Keywords": "assess*" OR "Author Keywords": "study" OR "Author Keywords": "experiment") AND ("Author Keywords": "github copilot" OR "Author Keywords": "ai pair programmer" OR "Author Keywords": "code assistant" OR "Author Keywords": "openai codex" OR "Author Keywords": "query recommendation" OR "Author Keywords": "code completion" OR "Author Keywords": "code intelligence" OR "Author Keywords": "code recommendation" OR "Author Keywords": "refactoring recommendation" OR "Author Keywords": "code generation" OR "Author Keywords": "import generation" OR "Author Keywords": "commit message generation" OR "Author Keywords": "code comment generation" OR "Author Keywords": "code documentation generation" OR "Author Keywords": "automatic program synthesis" OR "Author Keywords": "assert statement recommendation" OR "Author Keywords": "code summarization" OR "Author Keywords": "code summarisation" OR "Author Keywords": "language workbench" OR "Author Keywords": "bug fixing" OR "Author Keywords": "type recommendation" OR "Author Keywords": "modelling chatbot" OR "Author Keywords": "code synthesis"))
```

Listing 7: Scopus, submitted via the web UI (form).

```
TITLE—ABS—KEY ( ( "evaluat*" OR "assess*" OR "study" OR "experiment" ) AND ( "github copilot" OR "ai pair programmer" OR "code assistant" OR "openai codex" OR "query recommendation" OR "code completion" OR "code intelligence" OR "code recommendation" OR
```

refactoring recommendation" OR "code generation" OR "import generation" OR "commit message generation" OR "code comment generation" OR "code documentation generation" OR "automatic program synthesis" OR "assert statement recommendation" OR "code summarization" OR "code summarisation" OR "language workbench" OR "bug fixing" OR "type recommendation" OR "modelling chatbot" OR "code synthesis")) AND PUBYEAR > 2016 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "COMP")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "p") OR LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "j"))

Listing 8: SpringerLink, submitted via the Springer Nature API.

("evaluat*" OR "assess*" OR "study" OR "experiment") AND ("github copilot" OR "ai pair programmer" OR "code assistant" OR "openai codex" OR "query recommendation" OR "code completion" OR "code intelligence" OR "code recommendation" OR "refactoring recommendation" OR "code generation" OR "import generation" OR "commit message generation" OR "code comment generation" OR "code documentation generation" OR "automatic program synthesis" OR "assert statement recommendation" OR "code summarization" OR "code summarisation" OR "language workbench" OR "bug fixing" OR "type recommendation" OR "modelling chatbot" OR "code synthesis")

Appendix C Supplementary Material Selection Criteria

Table 14: Overview of artifact types and subcategories, including definitions and examples. The classification is primarily based on Pfeiffer [52], with the subcategories Platform-Independent Model (PIM), Computation-Independent Model (CIM), and Platform-Specific Model (PSM) derived from Lúcio et al. [53]. Code artifact purpose, representation, and notation are derived from [105] and defined as follows: Purpose refers to the specific role or function a code artifact serves within the software development lifecycle; Representation describes the form or structure in which the artifact exists, such as source code or binary files; Notation refers to the syntax, symbols, or formats used to represent the artifact.

Code				
Type	Purpose	Representation	Notation	Examples
Application Code (AC)	Application Implementation	Source	Textual	Java class definition unit, Python script, Matlab script, Jupyter notebook (code) cell, Java compilation unit, LLVM
Build Code (BC)	Build	Source	Textual	Makefile, Rakefile, Maven/ Gradle project descriptors, IDE project descriptors
Infrastructure Code (IC)	Infrastructure	Source	Textual	Dockerfile, Vagrantfile, GitHub/ GitLab pipeline descriptors
Design Code (DC)	Design	Source	Visual/ Textual	Platform-Specific Model (PSM; UML, BPMN, Ecore models) which contain details of software platforms and/ or are directly used by application code
Data				
Image	Image files used as resources or outputs (e.g., JPEG, SVG, PNG)			
Video	Video files used as resources or outputs (e.g., MP4, MAVI, MKV)			
Audio	Audio files used as resources or outputs (e.g., MP3, WAV)			
Configuration	Plain text files with file endings, such as ini, cfg, config			
Database	Binary files storing data from DBMS like SQLite, MySQL			
Font	Files for text rendering (e.g., TTF, OTF)			
Archive	(e.g., TAR, ZIP, RAR)			
Markup	Files that store data or serve as templates to be filled with more data (e.g., XML, HTML)			
Document	Artifacts used via/generated by an application (e.g., Excel, CAD) (no documentation)			
App Data	Files that store data for specific applications (e.g., diff output, Git indexes)			
Platform-Independent Model (PIM)	Models independent of any specific software platform, providing a high-level abstraction of the system, not being directly executed (processed) by a software platform or not being directly used by application code			
Machine Code	Any code not in a source representation, but a binary representation not directly manipulated by software developers			
Documentation				
Prose	Plain text files with a file extension (e.g., txt, md, adoc) or a representative name (e.g., README, NOTICE, CHANGELOG)			
Legalese	All text artifacts concerned with licenses, copyright notes, or patents			
Computation-Independent Model (CIM)	Models that focus on capturing the system’s environment and requirements without any consideration of computational details; not expressed using a software language			

Appendix D Publication List of First Analysis Round

Table 15: List of publications included in the first analysis round.

Venue	Publisher	Publication	Engine
Conference proceedings			
AITest	IEEE	[106]	IEEEExplore
AIware	ACM	[77]	Scopus
ACL	ACL	[107]	Scopus
ASE	IEEE	[37], [38], [89], [108], [109]	ACMDL, IEEEExplore, Scopus
ASIA CCS	ACM	[100]	ACMDL
CCS	ACM	[110]	Scopus
CHI	ACM	[73], [82], [83]	ACMDL
ICER	ACM	[111]	ACMDL
DSA	IEEE	[76]	IEEEExplore
EASE	ACM	[112], [113]	ACMDL
ETFA	IEEE	[99]	IEEEExplore
ESEC/FSE	ACM	[114], [115]	ACMDL, Scopus
HCI	Springer	[116]	SpringerLink
ICCP	IEEE	[75]	IEEEExplore
ICECET	IEEE	[68]	Scopus
ICLR	Open Access	[96]	Scopus
ICPC	ACM	[30]	IEEEExplore
ICSE	ACM	[29], [33]–[35], [117]–[124]	ACMDL, IEEEExplore, Scopus
ICSME	IEEE	[125], [126]	IEEEExplore, Scopus
ICST	IEEE	[127]	IEEEExplore
ETFA	IEEE	[128]	IEEEExplore
CIKM	ACM	[72]	ACMDL
MSR	IEEE	[40]	IEEEExplore
EMNLP-IJCNLP	ACL	[32]	Scopus
ISSTA	ACM	[95], [129]	ACMDL
IUI	ACM	[79]	Scopus
MAPS	ACM	[102]	ACMDL
NAACL	ACL	[130]	Scopus
NeurIPS	NeurIPS	[81]	Scopus
SAC	ACM	[131]	Scopus
SANER	IEEE	[88], [97], [132]	IEEEExplore, Scopus
SCAM	IEEE	[28]	IEEEExplore
SecDev	IEEE	[84]	IEEEExplore
USENIX	USENIX	[27]	Scopus
SLE	ACM	[74]	ACMDL
SP	IEEE	[26], [133]	IEEEExplore
SPLC	ACM	[78]	Scopus
Journals			
Trans. Comput. Hum. Interact.	ACM	[86]	ACMDL
Trans. Comput. Educ.	ACM	[94]	ACMDL
Algorithms	MDPI	[80]	Scopus
Applied Sciences	MDPI	[98]	Scopus
Empir. Softw. Eng.	Springer	[48], [49], [134]	Scopus, SpringerLink
Future Internet	MDPI	[135]	Scopus
Proc. Hum.-Comput. Interact.	ACM	[136]	ACMDL
IEEE Access	IEEE	[85], [87]	IEEEExplore, Scopus
Trans. Learn. Technol.	IEEE	[69]	IEEEExplore
Inf. Softw. Technol.	Elsevier	[92]	Scopus
Int. J. Educ. Technol. High Educ.	Springer	[137]	SpringerLink
J. Syst. Softw.	Elsevier	[42]	Scopus
J. Vis. Lang. Comput.	Elsevier	[44]	Scopus
Proc. Softw. Eng. (PACMSE)	ACM	[90], [138]	ACMDL
Trans. Dependable Secur. Comput.	IEEE	[67]	IEEEExplore
Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol. (TOSEM)	ACM	[45], [93], [139], [140]	ACMDL
Trans. Software Eng. (TSE)	IEEE	[46], [47], [70], [91], [141]–[143]	IEEEExplore, Scopus
Wirel. Networks	Springer	[71]	SpringerLink